

University of Gondar

College of Social Sciences and Humanities

Department of Journalism and Communication

**A Critical Analysis of The Front-Page Stories of *Addis Zemen*, *The Reporter* (Amharic)
and *Addis Admass* Newspapers**

By

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**A Critical Analysis of The Front-Page Stories of Addis Zemen, The Reporter (Amharic)
and Addis Admass Newspapers**

By

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**A thesis presented to the Department of Journalism and Communication in partial
fulfillment for the requirements of Master of Arts (MA) Degree in Journalism**

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November 2021

Declaration

I, **Addis Derbew Alie**, declare that this thesis entitled '**A Critical Analysis of The Front-Page Stories of Addis Zemen, The Reporter (Amharic) and Addis Admass Newspapers**', is entirely my original work, and it has not been submitted elsewhere either in partial or full requirement for another degree. All the sources and materials used in this work are properly cited and acknowledged.

Signature

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Date: 17/11/2021

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Approval Sheet

This is to certify that the thesis prepared by Addis Derbew entitled ‘**A Critical Analysis of the front-page stories of Addis Zemen, the Reporter (Amharic) and Addis Admass Newspapers**’, submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the Degree of Master of Arts in Journalism complies with the regulations of the university and meets the accepted standards concerning originality and quality.

Signed by Examining Committee:

Principal Advisor _____ Signature_____ Date_____

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External Examiner _____ Signature_____ Date_____

Internal Examiner _____ Signature_____ Date_____

Department Head_____ Signature _____ Date_____

Dedication

This work is dedicated in memory of my late mother w/ro Fikir Kassaw, even though you are not here today you were an amazing mother. I wish you were here on this day.

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank those of you who helped me with this thesis.

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Thirdly, I would like to thank my father Ato Derbew Alie, for your love and support. Thank you, my hero. I wish you a long live.

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List of acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviated forms	Full forms
E.C	Ethiopian calendar
EPRDF	Ethiopian People’s Revolutionary Democratic Front
AAU	Addis Ababa University
GERD	Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam
QuanCA	Quantitative Content Analysis
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Science
TPLF	Tigray People’s Liberation Front
UoG	University of Gondar
US	United States

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Abstract

The front page is the prime page to place the prioritized information. It is also a way of attracting readers. In cognizance of the importance of studying this prized page and the need for study on front-page issue coverage since the researcher found no prior study conducted on the same topic on the Ethiopian newspapers, this study was conducted on three Ethiopian newspapers: *Addis Zemen*, *The Reporter*, and *Addis Admass*. The objective of the study was to assess the front-page issue coverage; identify newsmakers and indicate news values employed on the front page of the sample newspapers from 10 December to 8 March 2021. To achieve these objectives, the researcher incorporated quantitative content analysis with interviews with the editors of the newspapers. By using multistage sampling, the study newspapers and the study period were decided. The researcher analyzed 122 stories and 107 news pictures that appeared on the front page of 42 newspaper editions. The study by incorporating the data from the content analysis and the interviews, found that the newspapers covered crucial occasional issues, however, in terms of actors/newsmakers, government officials dominate the front page, followed by the experts and professionals. Therefore, in this case, the sample newspapers failed to entertain multiple voices. Regarding the news values, timeliness was used chiefly in all three newspapers, followed by conflict, impact, and relevance. The researcher concluded the issues that were perceived important by the sample newspapers were the government, administration and politics; social and legal issues, and business, and finance issues.

Keywords: front-page, Ethiopian Newspapers, content analysis, issue salience, newsmakers, news values

Chapter One

Introduction

1. 1. Background of the Study

The findings of various studies on Ethiopian media in general and the print media, in particular, indicate that the Ethiopian print media more importantly, the ‘Government’ ones claimed to have been serving the governments in power from their very beginning. Zewge (2010), for example, stated the Ethiopian print media as “ever since the existence of the first Ethiopian newspaper *A'emro*, has been serving the government”.

On the other hand, the privately-owned print media, sometimes referred to as ‘Private’ print media, are claimed to have a lack of authentic sources. They also are claimed to side with opposition political parties and oppose the government. As a result of this, they are labeled, as “opposition publications” (Shimeles 2000).

Ashenafi (2012), who studied the framing of political parties during the 2010 Parliamentary Election by three newspapers *Addis Zemen* (Government-owned), *Awramba Times*, and *the Reporter*, both privately-owned), indicated that *awramba times* favored the opposition political party *Medrek*. *Addis Zemen* favored the then ruling party EPRDF while the reporter found it to be neutral.

Contrary to Ashenafi’s finding, the earlier studies on the Reporter newspaper claimed that the paper favored the EPRDF, claiming that the founder of the paper was one of the party people (e.g., Natnael, 2019).

Studies on *Addis Zemen* newspaper indicate that the newspaper has been also the *mouthpiece* of the state in power and this practice. For instance, Dawit, (2019) who studied the practice of press freedom of *Addis Zemen* newspaper before and after the ‘Reform’, indicated that the *Addis Zemen* was found to be the same before and after the “reform”. He

indicated that both before and after the ‘reform’ the newspaper faced a lack of information accessibility, diverse viewpoints, critique, independence, investigation.

Addis Admass privately-owned newspaper which once, according to (Mahlet, 2013), reached the highest level of circulation of 45,000 copies per week. In addition, it took a major proportion of market share than other competitive publication firms that participated in the same industry, is said to have relative independence. According to Desalegn and Destaw, (2016), this Newspaper had relatively better media freedom than the government-owned media to criticize the government.

On the other hand, *Addis Admass* tended to stay neutral rather than siding with either of the parties (the government or opposition) (Biruk & Walia, 2019; Dagim, 2019).

A lot of other studies on Ethiopian media indicate the *polarized* landscape of Ethiopian print media into a private-government dichotomy. The ‘private’ ones stand against the government, while the ‘government’ ones as for the ‘government’ (see e.g., Biruk & Walia, 2018; Dagim, 2013; Menychle, 2019; Nutman, 2016; Skjerdal, 2012; Zewge, 2010). Actually, the traditionally referred “Government media” are established in (The broadcasting Service Proclamation No.533/2007, as “Public broadcasting” whereas the private media are established as “commercial broadcasting”. The print media are also sometimes referred to as “public” or “government” vs. “commercial” or “private”. Therefore, since it is confusing to refer to the media sometimes government media, and other times government-owned, and private media; privately-owned, and other times commercial print newspaper, the researcher chose to use the term privately-owned (in this case *Addis Admass* and *The Reporter*) and government-owned (in this case, *Addis Zemen* newspaper) throughout the study.

Both the government-owned and the privately-owned newspapers are supposed to inform, educate and entertain the public about a variety of issues; nevertheless, different

studies indicated that the media prioritize politics over other issues in their coverage, while there were many other important issues in the country.

Concerning issue importance, it seems there are many issues common to African countries the public needs to be informed about. For instance, Ileri, Ongus, Mwititi, & Onsongo, (2017) in Kenya, evaluated the media coverage of issues in contrast with six issues with national importance (corruption, devolution, economic crisis, insecurity, poverty, and unemployment), and indicated in their findings that the selected newspapers had a low influence on the public regarding the six issues.

These issues are observable in Ethiopia too. Especially, issues such as poverty, unemployment, insecurity, ethnic conflicts, are common problems observed in Ethiopia. In this regard, these and other issues may be critical issues to the public to hear from the media. Even though this study did not consider the public opinion surveys, the researcher considers the real-world conditions in the country while dealing with media issue-importance. Hence, the current study is interested in assessing what issues are important for the Ethiopian print media. Since understanding the media issue's importance helps to understand the media position. To understand the media issue prioritization in the print media, paying attention to the front-page coverage is one of the cues. Although none of the above-reviewed studies focused on the front page of Ethiopian newspapers. The front page is the most important page of a newspaper where the most important information is placed on.

Merriam-Webster dictionary defines the front page as something Printed on the front page of a newspaper. [It is] also very newsworthy; First used in 1917. The stories that appear on the front page are the ones that will be talked about all day (www.wordpress.com, 2012). Likewise, Tewari (2014) indicated that the front page is a very important page for each newspaper. The front page is also regarded in many other studies as the crucial section of a

newspaper (e.g., Baah-Acheamfour, 2020; Kim & Chung 2017; Niemeyer; 2019; 2003; Reisner 1992; Utt & Pasternack).

That being the case, media organizations pay extra attention to some issues over others as they are meant to impact or set the agenda for their audience. For instance, as Behr & Iyengar, (1985) found out that in TV news, the lead stories were found to be more impactful than the non-lead stories.

According to Cox, (2014), newspapers also define some contents over others by using generally accepted hierarchical styles such as granting more space on a page, including larger headlines and additional features, such as graphics and photos.

Newspapers as a medium for in-depth and quality journalism provide the reader with valuable information. According to Fackler, (2003), enough people still enjoy paging through the news that the paper product is yet the most influential medium worldwide. However, as tried to state earlier, newspapers do not present all the content at equal emphasis. Placing some content on the front page of the newspapers, for instance, is regarded as a means of prioritizing some content. As McQuail (2010) also indicates how editors devote much time and energy to decide on what to place on the “prized page”. Therefore, this shows how editors signal to their readers which issues are the most important of the publications.

The stories appearing on the front are the ones that the media considered important to affect the public. The question of what issue is placed on this significant page matters for the public as the messages affect the public. In fact, the media agenda is not confined to influencing the public but also the policymakers, interest groups, and the policy itself (Cook, et al., 1983). Therefore, it is worth considering the issues that the media emphasized as by extension they are meant to influence the audience. Thus, this study assesses the coverage of the front-page issue of Ethiopian newspapers *Addis Zemen*, *The Reporter*, and *Addis Admass*.

When it comes to development, the Frontpage passed through different developments over time and the trend continues still today. Harrower & Elman, (2012, pp. 4-6) for instance indicated that the developments of newspaper front page design in different periods. Ranging from long gray eight columns in the 19th century; the introduction of bigger, bolder, and wider headlines in the early 20th century, to the use of different elements like color, information graphics, packaging, modular layout to make newspapers look fresh and attention-grabbing.

Studies show newspapers changed through time because of technological advances and competition in the market and other factors. For instance, Utt & Pasternack, (1986) indicated that the US daily newspapers had incorporated modern design formats with more color, oversized photos, and infographics on their front pages. Moreover, the readers perceived those newspapers with modern designs were better than traditional and modular ones.

Newspapers with the modern design were perceived by readers to be more pleasant; more important; more interesting; more informative; more responsible; better organized; more active; more colorful; fresher; more exciting; more professional; and neater while newspapers with the modular design were perceived to be more readable; bolder; less professional and more modern, the traditional were perceived to be more valuable; more accurate; running harder news; old-fashioned; more timid; staler; and duller than the modern and modular papers (Pasternack & Utt, 1986, pp. 31-32).

Moving on to the studies on the front page news, the earlier studies on the front page of newspapers tended to pay good attention to the content and less attention to visuals.(e.g., Bridges, 1989; Bridges & Bridges, 1997; Barnhurst & Nerone, 1991). While the recent studies, after the late 1990s, tend to focus on design changes and content presentation.

One may wonder why studying the front page of newspapers is so important. There are a set of elements on the front page that are worth studying. These are the design elements, such as infographics, colors, typographies, etc., and content elements such as news, features, lead stories, ads, syntax, etc... Because this page integrates many elements, that worth to be studied, even these days where web journalism is growing it is the area of study (see e.g.,

Cox, 2014; Costanza-Chock & Rey-Mazon, 2016; Küpper, 2020; Kim & Chung, 2017).

These days, circulation declined; many newspapers gave up their print publication; some even were shut down; some went online. As a result, editors are looking for new ways of content presentation and style of design for the front pages as much user-friendly, and navigable as possible.

On the one hand, some authors, like Küpper (2020) argue that the front page today is not as important as it was in the old days. This author further argues that unlike the old days the reader does not buy newspapers from kiosks; the reader these days gets the information from the web. On the other hand, some authors like Costanza-Chock & Rey-Mazon, (2016), who studied front pages using software named ‘pageOnex’ recently indicated that the front page is not only significant but also influences other platforms. Likewise, Bakker (2011) indicated that newspapers remained a significant source of information. However, the focus of this study is the stories and the news pictures that appear on the front: It did not consider other design elements such as colors graphics, etc., for the analysis.

The front page of the print edition of newspapers has long been and remains both a powerful indicator of the importance of a given story and a key mechanism for driving attention across all media platforms (Costanza-Chock & Rey-Mazon, 2016). This especially makes sense to Ethiopia where the mainstream newspapers including the sample newspapers and other newspapers such as *Addis fortune* and capital, prioritize the print edition even though they avail some contents and the print contents online.

Even though the front page has been studied well in different contexts in western newspapers, more specifically the US newspapers, the front page is the overlooked area of study which has not been given due attention in Ethiopia. It is, therefore, worth studying the front page here, for two reasons: one, studying the front page is an important way to understand which issues are covered in primary emphasis in consideration to the public's interest and the available crucial issues in the country, as the primary aim of this study is to examine media issue salience. Two, to fill the gap observed in this area and to forward recommendations for further studies.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

Newspaper is an important medium for the society, and the policymakers as well, in informing updating, entertaining, and educating, especially the front page of the newspaper carries the most relevant information of the day. As discussed in the earlier sections of this study, there is a large number of studies conducted on the front pages of the newspapers in other parts of the world (e.g., Erbring, Goldenberg, & Miller, 1980; Bridges, 1989; Barnhurst & Nerone, 1991; Reisner, 1992; Bridges, 1997; Utt & Pasternack, 2003; Costanza-Chock & Rey-Mazon, 2016; Kim & Chung, 2017; Niemeyer, 2019; Baah-Acheamfour, 2020). Yet, when it comes to Ethiopia, much attention has not been paid to the study of the front page. As far as the researcher's knowledge, only one related local study was found. Sintayehu, (2006) who studied the front-page design characteristics of English medium newspapers conducted the study. Sintayehu's study is different from the current study in that it examined the design/layout of the selected newspapers (*Ethiopian Herald, The Reporter, Capital, and Addis Fortune*). He concluded that the sample newspapers were found to be mainly dominated by horizontal design patterns, and he predicted the newspapers tended to change their design over time. The current study, unlike the former one, emphasizes on issue coverage on of the front page than the design matters and besides, the studied newspapers are different both in

medium and selected newspapers, except for *The Reporter* which the current researcher selected the reporter Amharic while the former selected the English medium.

In a general sense, the earlier studies conducted on Ethiopian newspapers were not emphasized on the front pages of the newspapers. The earlier studies on Ethiopian newspapers focused on how newspapers framed a certain issue, or the state of coverage of single-issue like election, famine, state of emergency, etc. For instance, a study conducted by Biruk & Walia, (2019) entitled “Framing (tone) in the newspaper coverage of Ethiopia during the state of emergency”, revealed that the government-owned newspapers framed the issues favorably, and the private ones were not as critical as the old days.

Bethlehem (2006) studied the framing of the 2002-2003 drought coverage of The Ethiopian Herald, Reporter, Fortune, and Addis Admass newspapers. By using content analysis, she found the newspapers used higher event and appeal frames compared to diagnostic and prognostic frames.

The reviewed studies on Ethiopian newspapers emphasized on the frames; coverage of a single topic issue, or event. The current study, unlike the earlier studies, emphasized on the type of issues that were covered prominently, the newsmakers frequently appeared in the front-page stories and the types of news values that were employed dominantly.

Accordingly, to understand the media issue salience studying the front page of newspapers here is a good way. This study examined the issue coverage of the selected newspapers on the front page. In relation, how the stories were selected and what influences (gate keeps) or the selection of the stories was also the concern of this study. Concerning the influence of the issue selection process on the front page, the type of news values employed to select the story was investigated. As news values employed influence the news to be selected. According to Harcup & O’Neill, (2017, p. 1470), “News values are worth studying because they inform the mediated world that is presented to news audiences, providing a

shared shorthand operational understanding of what working journalists are required to produce to deadlines”.

1.3. Objectives of the study

1.3.1. General objective

The general objective of this study is to analyze the front-page issue coverage of the *Addis Zemen*, *The Reporter* (Amharic), and *Addis Admass* newspapers

1.3.2. Specific objectives

The study aims to achieve the following specific objectives

1. To identify the issues which are deemed significant in the selected Ethiopian Newspapers
2. To disclose the newsmakers of the front-page stories
3. To explore the types of news values employed to the selected Ethiopian newspapers’ front-page stories

1.4. Research Questions

This study strived to answer the following research questions:

1. What types of issues are featured on the selected newspapers' front page?
2. Who are the major newsmakers in the stories?
3. Which types of news values are employed in the front-page stories of the selected newspapers?

1.5. Significance of the study

This study helps to understand the nature of the stories that appear, and the newsmakers/actors, that make news and the news values employed on the front page of sample newspapers. Secondly, this study filled a knowledge gap about the types of news values used in Ethiopian newspapers, and thirdly, this study can be used as a reference for further studies on the newspapers especially, the front page. Furthermore, this study indicated the use of news pictures on the front page by the sample newspapers.

1.6. Scope of the Study

The scope of this study is limited to the print medium because of time and budget constraints to include all the media outlets. In fact, broadcast media is the common type of media in a country like Ethiopia where there is a high illiterate rate and a vast majority of the population live in rural areas. Newspapers are selected for the study because the researcher believes that since the newspapers are a literate's medium, they carry quality and in-depth information so that they carry a lot of information to explore. In addition, newspapers were selected because of their availability for the study. As in the case of broadcast media, recorded programs could be lost and it could be difficult to get data for longer periods. Hence, newspapers were chosen over the broadcast media, and still including all the available newspapers is a difficult task to analyze, so this study purposely selected only three newspapers. These are one government-owned daily newspaper -Addis Zemen, two privately

owned newspapers Addis Admass (weekly), and the reporter Amharic (bi-weekly). The newspapers under study were selected based on their relatively larger circulation; their geographical distribution, plus all the three newspapers are of the Amharic medium, which are relatively read by the larger audience. All available front-page stories of sampled newspaper issues were put under the subject of the study.

1.7. Limitations of the Study

Even though there are many privately owned and government-owned newspapers in Ethiopia published in different languages, the researcher purposively picked only three Amharic language newspapers because of time and financial constraints. Moreover, the study was restricted to only four months of data; it would produce comprehensive results and would enable the researcher to conclude the results to the larger population if the study was conducted on larger data and longer study periods. Lastly, this study would produce even better results if the study included public opinion surveys. Because of the constraints stated, the study did not incorporate public opinion surveys.

Chapter Two

Review of Related Literature and Theoretical Frameworks

Introduction

This chapter discusses the previous studies conducted on the same topic and the theoretical frameworks that guide this study. This chapter attempts to discuss major studies and findings that were conducted on the Front-page of newspapers in different parts of the world and, Ethiopia.

2.1. Review of Previous Studies on Front-Pages of Newspapers

Bridges (1989), studied the news use on the front page of 101 US daily newspapers to describe if there was a certain pattern of news use in terms of news “attributes” (i.e., timeliness, prominence, proximity, impact, conflict, oddity, magnitude). The author by measuring the space provided to each story type, he identified timeliness as most important in front-page news, followed by prominence and then proximity as opposed to the results of prior studies, which claimed conflict (clashy-type of stories) as a common type of stories.

Bridges & Bridges (1997), did a replication of the news use on the front page of US newspapers from 1986-1993. In consideration of three factors, the advancement of technology; the changes in population demographics; and the competition in the market during the mid-to-late 1980s and early 1990s, they re-examined the news use on the front page and they found out almost similar pattern to their prior study. With a little increase in the use of proximity (local stories) about 4 percentage points, and impact stories increased about 3%. Timeliness, prominence, and proximity appeared most often, although proximity still appears in little more than half of the front-page space.

Corrigan, (1990) also studied the news values coding of lead stories on the front page by content analyzing more than 900 stories taken from two national and two regional newspapers indicated that *news stories can be sorted more easily by certain values-such as conflict, proximity, and prominence-than by the traditional five Ws and H*. These studies of Bridges (1989) and Bridges & Bridge (1997) examined the news use in terms of news attributes or sometimes referred to as news determinants or news values by measuring the space provided to each story type. While Corrigan's study was delimited to analyzing, only lead stories. While the current study considers the whole, front-page stories of the selected Ethiopian newspapers to achieve three objectives these were: what issues are deemed significant, who the newsmakers in the stories are, and what types of news values are employed. The method is measuring the total number of story types covered in percentage, in doing so the study achieved these objectives. Other authors such as Erbring, Goldenberg, & Miller, (1980) studied Front-Page News and Real-World Cues, and these authors argued that taking agenda-setting, more importantly, political agenda-setting as "an overall ranking of issues, has not shed much light on the processes linking public issue salience to varying media attention". Instead, they attempted to introduce the "audience effect model which treats issue-specific sensitivity of audiences." The model the authors utilized, deals with the audience effect of issue preference where the audience has a different taste of issues. In this case, the issues that the media deemed important may not be to the audience. Contrasting to the earlier studies on agenda-setting, the authors concluded that, the media agenda is not a sufficient condition to affect the audience, as there might be a variety of issues that the citizens are concerned with. However, they did not deny that the media could inform the citizens about the world beyond the reach of direct experience. This study of Erbring, Goldenberg, & Miller, (1980) introduced an interesting concept, *audience effect*, which deals with individual taste of issues, which they call it *sensitizing* and *desensitizing*. Individuals

indeed have different issue tastes, however; it is still inevitable for the individuals to be affected by the media agenda. As the public agenda is affected by the media agenda; for example, Behr & Iyengar, (1985) studied the Television News, Real-World Cues, and Changes in the Public Agenda, and pointed out that the public agenda was affected by the media content that the editors and the journalists chose to present to their audience. These authors did not only indicate the fact that the media affects the public agenda they also found out that the media agenda comes from the real-world cues apart from individuals issue salience or concern. Another interesting finding of the study of Behr & Iyengar is that all the news stories have not equal impact. The lead stories were found to have the strongest impact on citizens' perceptions of issue importance than other non-lead news stories. This is because the lead stories in the broadcast news are considered the most significant news of the day. In this regard, the lead stories in TV news are like the front-page stories that of the newspapers.

When it comes to Africa, Baah-Acheamour, (2020), conducted a study on the front page of the Ghanaian newspaper using qualitative content analysis. The researcher examined the Ghanaian times newspaper as state-owned media if it had performed the country's constitutional obligation of the media to cover a variety of issues and entertain diverse viewpoints of views. The results indicated that the newspaper devoted much coverage to political news, and elites dominated the coverage in terms of actors in the news.

Baah-Acheamfour's study is rather related to the current study in some ways: one, since it is related to the current study in that, it examined the front-page coverage of the newspaper; timewise, it was conducted in 2020, this may suggest that the front page of newspapers is still a study area in Africa. As tried to mention in the earlier sections, the study of front pages is tending to the online newspapers. Some studies are interested in comparing online and traditional newspapers. For instance, Cox, (2014) compared content prioritization in print and online newspapers. Other authors Costanza-Chock & Rey-Mazon, (2016)

introduced software called PageOneX, which helps to code, analyze and visualize the newspaper's, front-pages. However, in the case of African countries like Ethiopia where there are no online-only or *digital-first* newspapers, and where the mainstream newspapers including the sample newspapers and other newspapers such as *Addis fortune* and *Capital*, prioritize the print edition over the digital one. Even though they avail some digital content and print editions online the traditional formats are still a priority. Furthermore, much has not been done on the front page issue coverage of the Ethiopian newspapers, so the researcher believed that it was appropriate to consider the print content over the online content for the study.

Even though Baah-Acheamfour's study is related to the current study, it is different from the current study in that it was conducted to check if the state-owned newspaper- *Ghanian Times* performed its constitutional obligation to cover a variety of issues, different social classes, the study was also interested in investigating the geographical distribution of the stories, and the news values that influence the story selection. Methodologically the study employed a qualitative approach.

The current study examined the front page of the selected Ethiopian newspapers,(government-owned *Addis Zemen*, two privately-owned newspapers, *Addis Admass*, and *The Reporter*). This study uses a mixed research approach. The main difference lies in that this study is interested in assessing media issue salience than the constitutional obligation of the media to perform. Besides, there were no prior studies that indicated whether or not the front-page coverage of Ethiopian newspapers shares similar trends with the front-page study of other African countries. Therefore, this study is intended to fill the gap observed on this topic in Ethiopia.

2.2. Use of pictures in the front-page stories

A memorable saying, “a picture is worth a thousand words” embodies that news pictures are very important for both aesthetics and content. Aesthetically, they make a page attractive so that the reader wants to read the story. Contentwise they make the message complete and memorable.

The contents presented in the newspapers and magazines cannot convey a complete message without using pictures (Simbiat). Furthermore, (Harrower & Elman, 2013) indicated the use of pictures in the front-page stories is a way of grabbing the attention of the readers. “Using Photographs in Newspaper enhance the credibility of the stories. As they depict reality, and furnish evidence to show the authenticity of a news story or give proof of an event that occurred” (Jennifer, 2008, p. 13).

The following photographs are the most common types of photos in journalism (Kobre (2004) cited in Jennifer, (2008); newsmoor.com, 2018).

- **Spot News:** These are pictures that carry urgent, unplanned, and often unpleasant or undesirable occurrences. Spot news pictures include car accidents, plane crashes, fires, murders, bank robberies, etc.
- **General News photojournalism:** Unlike spot news, general news pictures are recorded events or planned events pictures and they are less time-sensitive they can be delayed and yet not go stale. Photographs on general news include politics, press, or social events, must portray something new or exhibit other news value such as prominence, magnitude, oddity, etc.
- **Features Photograph:** Features provide a visual break from routine news pictures. They tell an old story in a new way or from a new point of view. Editors

tend to use features when space is available and they have no images of a more severe and essential nature.

- **Portraits/personality photos:** They are used to tell a person's story. Photojournalists shoot both posed and candid portraits to achieve this. Even when they are arranged elements for portraits, photojournalists look for honest, candid moments. Portraits reveal something about a person's personality thus photojournalists strive to project this in their portrait pictures.
- **Sports Photograph:** Sports photographers are like athletes, they uniquely strive to capture the fast-paced action and drama of competition. A sports picture summarizes the game in one photograph on time. The sports photographer captures interesting, unusual, emotional, and unexpected actions on and of the sports field.
- **Photo Story/pictorial journalism:** This refers to editorial photographs that tell narrative stories. For many photojournalists, telling stories with pictures is the ultimate professional experience. The story must be planned and well organized to present a complete detailed account of an interesting and significant subject, event, and personality aspect of contemporary life in a narrative form. Sometimes stories can be built in a matter of minutes, other times it takes months or years.
- **Illustration photo Journalism:** this type of photo refers to combined or manipulated images that create a 'new' image. advertising photographers to illustrate stories based on issues and abstract ideas. Such as economics, science, etc. Photo illustrations communicate concepts a literal picture is not always able to.

In the case of the current study, the researcher adopted the above 7 types of pictures to analyze the news pictures of the front page. Furthermore, the study analyzed the pictures

concerning the type of issues demonstrated with pictures and the types of actors/newsmakers featured in the front pictures of the newspapers. As pictures play significant roles in making a certain story more credible and more readable, this study considers the stories that are presented with pictures are deemed the most significant ones by the newspapers.

Additionally, the actors/newsmakers that are featured in the pictures are the ones that are considered the major newsmakers/actors.

2.3. Placement of the front-page stories

Story placement is another crucial issue when talking about issue salience. Some scholars such as Benton & Frazier, (1976); Lopez-Escobar, Llamas, & McCombs, (1998) argue that amount of stories published and the space dedicated to the stories indicate the attention the media give to certain issues. Kiouisis(2004) on the other hand, argues that the position and placement of the stories are more paramount characteristics than the amount and the space dedicated to certain issues. As discussed in the previous sections placing contents on the front page is a way of signaling that some contents are prioritized over the others. However, it does not necessarily indicate that all the stories placed on the front page are presented at equal prominence. Lim, (2010) for instance, indicated that the most prominent stories may appear on the top area of the front page and other stories may appear below the fold. In these cases, the number of stories published on the front pages is not enough condition to measure the salience. A study of readers' eye-tracking by Outing & Ruel (2004), revealed that the readers' eyes “most often fixated first in the upper left of the page, then hovered in that area before going left to right. Only after perusing the top portion of the page for some time did their eyes explore further down the page” (Outing & Ruel 2004,p.2).

Figure 1: The eye movement pattern of the readers(Outing & Ruel,2004)

Many studies (e.g.Küpper, 1990; Garcia and Stark, 1991; Hansen, 1994; Holmqvist and Wartenberg, 2005 cited in Leckner, (2012)found that readers of printed newspapers typically make their first fixation on the right page of a spread.

Considering the organizations' preferences for the positioning/placement of the larger headlines; main pictures, and the incorporation of other elements of the stories, the upper right page of the newspaper is most of the time considered as the place where the very important stories are placed on.

In the case of this study, four placements were adopted from different literatures. These are: 1) The upper left: the left topmost page above the fold; 2) Bottom left: below the fold; 3) upper right (above the fold), and 4) bottom right (below the fold).

2.4. Newsmakers /Actors in the News

Collins dictionary defines Newsmaker as people or things or sometimes an event that figures largely in a news report. The newsmaker /actors in the news are used interchangeably throughout this study as they both indicate the same concept although some prefer to refer to

actors(e.g Masini & Aelst, 2017; Beckers & Aelst, 2018) while others refer to newsmakers(e.g soley,1992). Newsmakers may include government officials, ordinary citizens, politicians, etc. who are allowed to talk in the story about a certain topic. As to Beckers & Aelst, (2018), there traditionally were two categories of newsmakers: the ‘elite/official and non-elite/unofficial source’, what Gans, (2004/1979) in other words calls the ‘knowns’ and ‘unknowns. Beckers & Aelst argue for the need for more aggregate categories citing previous studies. Consequently, they developed four categories. These are political and governmental actors; experts and professionals; civil society organizations and citizens which could be further categorized into more specific actors as follows:

Government and politics: these include government officials and civil servants, politicians, law enforcement officers emergency service personnel; Professionals and experts, including media and journalists, business professionals. experts, academics, and celebrities; Civil society organizations, this includes a representative of social organizations or interest groups; and Citizens, this includes involved (victims, or eyewitnesses, or all ordinary citizens that appear on the news)and involved citizens (have no representative function on regarding the news event)

(Beckers & Aelst, 2018, pp. 3-4)

The current researcher developed six categories: experts and professionals, government officials and politicians, public figures and celebrities, civil society organizations, ordinary people, and others. Probably, these are the most common categories of newsmakers that appear in different studies. Here, added to the Beckers & Aelst category is the “other”, this category is included to make the analysis more open for possible uncategorized newsmakers. The civil society organization category is adapted from the above-mentioned authors. The rest are developed based on other studies and the objectives the research intends to achieve.

Understanding who is allowed to speak in the news is a central topic in journalism studies (Beckers & Aelst, 2018). Studies of content diversity focus on the importance of having a variety of voices in the news and analyze the diversity of actors that get the opportunity to have their say and convey their point of view (Gans,2004).

According to Masini & Aelst, (2017), having diverse actors in the story is the precondition for promoting social pluralism. Moreover, diversity of content or viewpoints in the news provides the reader with a variety of perspectives on a certain topic. Apart from increasing the range of viewpoints, understanding who is talking in the news tells how the news is shaped (Soley, 1992). Soley described newsmakers in contrast to news shapers as newsmakers are identified as people who speak from a certain side of the event or controversy and by extension, the stories are reports of what these people have said or done while news shapers are presented as outsiders (detached) analysts which the media refer as “experts”, “scholars” or "specialists”.

2.5. News Values

News values are defined in different ways by different scholars. For instance, Bednarek & Caple, (2014), define news values from journalism, and communication studies perspective, as “properties of events or stories or as criteria/principles that are applied by news workers to select events or stories as news or to choose the structure and order of reporting”. They also, see news values from the linguistics perspective as “the newsworthy aspects of actors, happenings and issues as existing in and constructed through discourse”(Bednarek & Caple 2014, pp.136- 137)

When talking about the news values, one never forgets these two names, Galtung and Ruge. These authors use the concept to describe how the events are selected as news, more specifically the foreign news in the Norwegian press.

According to Kepplinger, (2008) Galtung & Ruge, (1965) and Östgaard, (1965) developed ‘the theory of news values’ and other authors such as Rosengren (1970, 1977), Schulz (1976), Staab (1990), and Shoemaker (1996) made theoretical and methodological developments, while he acknowledged Lippman(1961) for first introducing the concept of “news values”.

According to Ittefaq, (2019, p. 85), News value and news factors theory is applicable, universally, to understand news selection and publishing. Other authors also agree on the influence of news values on media’s selection of news (see, e.g., Bednarek & Caple, 2014; Harcup & O’Neill, 2001, 2017).

Harcup & O’Neill, (2017), indicated the need for studying the news values by mentioning the fact that news values inform the mediated world which is presented to the news audience.

Even though the Galtung-Ruge’s 12 news factors are universally applicable and landmark for other studies on the area, they as Harcup & O’Neill(2001), noted, are also problematic at some point; they are hypothetical, and they have limitations when applying for domestic news as their focus was the foreign news.

2.5.1. List of the Galtung -Ruge’s 12 news factors

F1. Frequency: if the event happening falls at the same time as the media’s time-span or schedule, the event has a chance of being selected as news.

F2. Threshold: the greater the intensity of the incident the probable the event being selected as news.

F3. Unambiguity: the clearer, Unambiguous or understandable the event is, the more probable the event is worth considering to be in the news.

F4. Meaningfulness: this implies that if the event has cultural proximity, or closeness and gives sense meaning that if it is relevant to the listening or reading audience, then the event probably will be in the news.

F5. Consonance: the more consonant or acceptable the event with the audience the more probable that it will be in the news.

F6. Unexpectedness: the more deviant or unexpected the event is, the more worth considering to be recorded as news.

F7. Continuity: if the event once has been in the news, it will likely continue to be in the news.

F8. Composition: if more items have been included in the news, they be will likely to selected as news.

Of the 12 news factors the above eight factors which the authors indicated, are ‘culture-free, and should not depend on cultural parameters; however, the following four factors, they said are ‘culture-bound (pp. 67-68). Yet *F4.*, meaningfulness seems culturally bound as for an event to be in news it should give a sense for the culture of reading or listening audience.

F9. Reference to elite nations: The more the event concerns elite nations, the more probable that it will become a news item.

F10. Reference to elite people: The more the event concerns elite people, the more probable that it will become a news item.

F11. Reference to persons: The more the event can be seen in personal terms, as due to the action of specific individuals, the more probable that it will become a news item.

F12. Reference to something negative: The more negative the event in its consequences, the more probable that it will become a news item (Galtung & Ruge, 1965, p. 68).

Harcup & O'Neill (2001), by further questioning and examining Galtung and Ruge's 12 news factors, came up with a revised list of news values. These are the power elite: stories about powerful individuals or institutions; celebrity: stories concerning famous people; entertainment: stories with entertaining elements such as animals, showbiz, photography; surprise: stories with an element of surprise or contrast; bad news: stories involving conflict or tragedy; good news: stories about positive tones, such as rescues; magnitude: stories that are significant enough both in the number of people involved in and the impact they have on the audience; relevance: stories about issues, people nations, groups perceived to be relevant to the audience; follow-ups: stories about the subjects that are already in the news; and newspaper agenda stories that reflects the newspaper's agenda(pp.19-18).

Harcup & O'Neill (2001) made the review of Galtung and Ruge's news factors and attempted to make the news values work for the selection of the domestic news, which they claim Galtung and Ruge ignored the day-to-day reporting. The other gaps that the authors mentioned that the Galtung and Ruge 12 factors did not address were; their new factors being event-oriented, their focus was on how the events, more importantly, the foreign news when as different literatures suggest and as their findings indicated, the news is not all about an event; some of the stories that are other than event-oriented are, entertainment, positive news, stories about elite people or institution, and stories written of the media organization's agenda.

The researcher adapted Melvin Mencher's commonly used news values (i.e., Timeliness, impact, Prominence, Proximity, conflict, Unusual/oddity) and from the Harcup & O'Neill's 10 news values, the researcher found only four of them (i.e., the newspaper agenda, positive news, bad news, and Relevance), worth to adapted into the categories(see Appendix A). The rest such as the entertainment, celebrity, the power elite, seem more topical or associated with actors in the news these categories are included in the other categories of the

coding book of this study: the ‘news actors’ category (celebrity, the power elite), and ‘theme’ category (entertainment).

Apart from the Melvin Mencher (2012) and Harcup & O’Neill (2001) news values, the researcher considers the findings of the previous researches on the news values. So, the list of the news values is adapted from multiple sources. For instance, Corrigan, (1990), found that “news stories can be sorted more easily by certain values- such as conflict, proximity, and prominence than by the traditional five “Ws and H”. In Ethiopia’s case, Semere (2010, identified Timelines, prominence, impact, and proximity, unusual.

List of News Values incorporated into the study

1. **Timelines:** stories that are written of recently, happen, or happen shortly.
2. **Conflict:** stories about Strife, antagonism, and warfare, ethnic clashes, conflict of interests among individuals or groups, controversies, arguments, and fights.
3. **Impact:** Events that are likely to affect many people; Stories that are perceived as sufficiently significant that include greater numbers of people involved and impact the greater number of people.
4. **Prominence:** stories written of public figures, well-known people, celebrities, etc...
5. **Relevance:** Stories about issues, groups, and nations perceived to be relevant to the audience
6. **proximity:** Events that are geographically or emotionally close to people.
7. **Unusual/oddity:** Events that deviate sharply from the expected, that departs considerably from the experiences of everyday life make news
8. **Newspaper agenda:** Stories that set or fit the news organization’s agenda, whether ideological, commercial, or as part of a specific campaign.
9. **Good news:** Stories with particularly positive overtones such as recoveries, breakthroughs, cures, wins, and celebrations.

10. **Bad News:** Stories with particularly negative overtones such as death, injury, defeat, and loss (of a job, for example)

2.6. Theoretical frameworks

2.6.1. Agenda-setting theory

The term ‘agenda-setting’, is always associated with these two scholars, McCombs and Shaw. According to Dearing & Rogers,(1992), the term agenda-setting first appeared in the article entitled ‘the agenda-setting function of the mass media’ by McCombs and Shaw in 1972. Even though the concept has long been noticed, by Walter Lippman (1922) in his work entitled ‘public opinion’, whereby stated the concept as “the pictures in our heads and the world outside”. That is to describe the mediated reality and the real world. McCombs and Shaw expanded the concept and introduced the term ‘agenda-setting’ to describe the correlation between the media issue coverage of the 1968 US presidential election campaign and the salience of the issue of the Chapel Hill voters. McCombs and Shaw found out that the issues that the media emphasized during the campaign were found to be important issues for the voters too.

Accordingly, they used the term ‘agenda-setting’ to describe that the media might determine or *set* the *agenda* for the public in reflecting what the candidates said during the campaign.

2.6.1.1. Basic agenda setting /first-level agenda setting. At this level, the agenda-setting function of the media is to signal important issues to the public. As Cohen (1963), quoted by these authors, notes that “the press may not be successful much of the time in telling people what to think, but it is stunningly successful in telling its readers what to think about” (see also., Coleman, McCombs, Shaw, & Weaver, 2009; McCombs, 2005).

Furthermore, McCombs, (2011) also indicates, media in general, give a host of cues about the salience of topics. In the case of newspapers, they signal the issue salience in the daily news by placing a lead story on page one, and by displaying large headlines, etc. In the case of television news, the opening story on a newscast, the length of time devoted to a certain story, etc., are some cues, and by repeating these cues day after day the media effectively communicate the issue's importance in such a way media can have the public's attention, then make the public talk about that group of small issues. One of the perfect examples of the agenda-setting function of the media as stated in Griffin, (2012) is the ‘Watergate issue’ which the *Washington Post* achieved in making the issue the concern of the public by placing it on the front page for months.

2.6.1.2. Attribute agenda setting /Second-level agenda-setting. McCombs, (2005), argues that at this level, the media is not only successful in telling what to think about the issue salience but also, they can be successful in telling us how to think about it. In this sense, the second-level agenda setting is similar to framing theory in that both framing and attribute-agenda-setting or second-level agenda-setting emphasizes the perspective of the communicators and the audience, how they picture or shape the content of the messages.

Apart from the above two levels of agenda-setting, McCombs, Shaw, & Weaver, (2014) added more levels to contemporary researches; among these are, network-agenda setting (third-level), and agenda melding. Network agenda-setting deals with “the impact of the networked media agenda of *objects* or *attributes* on the networked public agenda of an

object or attribute salience”, while agenda melding deals with the way we merge the civic agendas of the media and our valued reference communities with our personal views and experience to create a satisfying picture of the world.

In the case of this study, the researcher evaluates the sampled newspapers with the first level agenda-setting using content analysis. What issues are being prioritized or emphasized are the focuses of the present study. Issues that appear on the front page frequently are considered the most important issues of the media.

2.6. 2. Gatekeeping Theory

“Gatekeeping is the process of culling and crafting countless bits of information into a limited number of messages that reach the people each day, and it is the center of the media’s role in modern public life” (Shoemaker & Vos, 2009, p. 1). The core assumption of this theory is that the issues that appear as news are the ones that are granted to pass the gate.

Different instances shape and influence the media messages. For instance, Reese, (2001) in his article, hierarchies of influences indicates how the media content is influenced at three levels these namely. individual level, routine level, and organizational level.

At the individual level, we view the attitudes, training, and background of the journalist (or media worker more generally) as influential. [...]. Individuals do not work alone, however, or use rules they invent themselves. The routines level of analysis considers the constraining influences of work practices. ‘Routines’ are patterned practices that work to organize how we perceive and function within the social world. [...]. At the organizational level, we may consider the goals and policies of a larger social structure and how power is exercised within it (Reese, 2001, p.179-181).

Therefore, the media content is subjected to different levels of influences and it is filtered at different phases ranging from an individual level to the routine and the organization level.

As much as individuals (journalists/reporters) play a significant role in deciding which information becomes news etc., however, when it comes to selecting the stories for the front page, it is believed to be the task of the editors.

“How are stories actually selected for the front page? For the most part, this basic gatekeeping task is carried out by editors in the context of a daily staff meeting known as the editorial conference” (Clayman & Reisner, 1998, p. 178).

In light of that, concerning how the stories are selected and placed, the researcher conducted an in-depth interview with the editors in chief of the selected newspapers to explore the views of the editors on how and why they select a certain issue over the others.

Chapter Three

Methodology of the Study

Introduction

This chapter presents the research methodology that employs for the execution of this study. It discusses the methodological approach, the design, the sample size, and the sampling techniques of the study that have been employed. It also introduces the process of data collection that has been used, the data collection instruments that have been employed, and data analysis methods that have been applied.

3.1 Approaches of the study

This study used the mixed research methodology. Because combining the qualitative and quantitative methods reduce, the limitation of either method when they are used alone (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). So accordingly, the purpose of employing this concurrent mixed method is to investigate the types of salient issues covered on the newspapers' front page. In the study, the quantitative content analysis was used to collect the data from the newspapers by using standardized coding sheets/manuals. At the same time, the interviews were conducted with chief editors of the newspapers to explore issues related to how and why the editors select stories for the front page. by using semi-structured interview guide questions (see appendix C).

3.2. Design of the study

Research designs are plans and the procedures for research that span the decisions from broad assumptions to detailed methods of data collection and analysis (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). This study employed a descriptive design, most precisely a concurrent triangulation strategy. As the essence of descriptive research design is to answer the questions such as what and how so did this study was intended to inquire the type of issues that were

deemed important for the media. Additionally, it is also because both quantitative and qualitative data of the study were gathered concurrently. To meet the objective, the researcher incorporated quantitative content analysis and interview techniques. Moreover, the gathered data have been analyzed/ interpreted descriptively.

Concurrent Triangulation design

Concurrent Triangulation design is a design whereby the researcher collects both quantitative and qualitative data concurrently. Then compares the two databases to determine if there is convergence, differences, or some combination, the data collected separately via the qualitative and quantitative methods are merged during the data analysis and discussion. The importance of this design is that it fills the gap that occurs while using one method alone, and produces well-validated and substantiated findings. In most cases, equal weight is given for both methods, however, in some cases, one method might be a priority while the other might be supplementary (see, Creswell & Creswell, 2018, p.194-98).

In the case of this study, the content analysis is the primary method, and the data collected via the interview supports the finding and is triangulated together.

3.3. The Universe of the Study

According to Wimmer & Dominick, (2011), defining the universe in content analysis is about specifying the boundaries of the body of content, and the period the study considers. Accordingly, contentwise, this study considered all stories and all the news pictures that appeared on the front pages of the sample newspapers. To operate the content analysis, first, the physical newspaper editions were collected from the newspaper vendors at Arat kilo. Some missing physical newspapers (*Addis Zemen and The Reporter*) were not found from the sellers due to the length of time. Thus the newspapers' print editions (PDF form) were accessed using the website of the newspapers.

Concerning the period, the researcher selects the period *Tahisas1-2013- Megabit 30, 2013 E.C.* (10 December 2020 to March 8, 2021). This period is purposively selected assuming that during this period, the newspapers cover relatively diverse issues than the periods excluded. As the study was interested in examining issue coverage of the media on regular days rather than coverage of issues with specific happenings, such as election, drought, state of emergency, etc.,

As Lynch & peer, (2002), suggests avoiding monumental news events that radically change coverage, major holidays, extraordinary special sections, or anything else that alters more than ten percent of content from the usual. Hence, the researcher attempted to exclude the months before December, as there were major happenings in the country such as the conflict between the Tigray regional state and federal government on November 4, 2020. Then followed the “legal enforcement operation”, which lasts for about a month from (Tikimt 24,2013 E.C.), right after the attack on the North command of Ethiopian National defense force by TPLF military operation on November 4, 2020. The end of the operation was announced on November 29, 2020 (Hidar 20-2013 E.C.,). The months after megabit are excluded as the 6th Ethiopian national election 2021 was scheduled at the end of Ginbot (*Ginbot 28,2013*) which were later postponed to *sene, 14 2013 E.C.,*). The researcher assumed that after *megabit*, the newspapers may give prominence to election issues, such as electoral debate, registration of voters, etc., accordingly the publications after megabit were excluded.

All the issues of these papers published during the entire study period from *Tahisas1-megabit 30, 2013 E.C.,* (December 10, 2020, to march 8, 2021) were considered as the population. The researcher drew 42 samples from a population of 168 newspaper issues.

3.4.Sampling Techniques, Procedures, and Sample size

3.4.1.Sampling Techniques

3.4.1.2.Multistage sampling. Sampling in content analysis is often multistage (Drisko & Maschi, 2016; Wimmer & Dominick, 2014). That is, the researchers initially selects a specific set of texts or files, then within this material identify subunits of interest. In light of this, the researcher employs multistage sampling through different phases. First of all, the period of the study and newspapers were selected purposively. The study period is selected as a regular period coverage with no reference to specific happening as stated earlier. The sampling of newspapers under study is made in consideration of; their geographical distribution, as the papers, are distributed across the country circulation of the newspapers for they have relatively larger circulation in the country (The broadcasting Service Proclamation No.533/2007). Furthermore, since the language of publications of all the three newspapers in the Amharic language, the researcher believes that the newspapers reach and impact more readers than English and other languages newspapers in the country. secondly, the newspapers are further categorized into stratum based on their frequency of publications, thirdly a sample is drawn from each stratum representative of the stratum.

3.4.1.2.1. Proportionate stratified random sampling. Proportionate stratified random sampling is a probability sampling method in which different strata in a population are identified and in which the number of elements drawn from each stratum is proportionate to the relative number of elements in each stratum (Law, 2009). According to Krippendorff (2004), stratified sampling recognizes distinct subpopulations (strata) within a population. In the case of newspapers, newspapers can be categorized by different strata such as the size of readership and, frequency of publication. This study used the second one. Accordingly, the sampled newspapers were categorized by their frequency of publication (daily, bi-weekly, and weekly,). Since the sampled newspapers were of different strata by frequency of

publication, the available size of populations was not even. As stated earlier, Addis Zemen has 120 (71.4%); The Reporter 32(19.04%); Addis Admass 16 (9.52%) of the total population. So, to make samples representative of each stratum and make the samples proportional, the researcher used the stratified proportionate random sampling technique as suggested by Haque, (2010, p.3), for calculating the sample size of each stratum according to their percentage share in the population. This can be done by multiplying the sample number by their percentage proportion. In this case, the number of samples decided is 42(25%) from a total population of 168 which is of the total population newspaper issues: the size is determined based on Wimmer & Dominick (2011), a suggestion that 10% to 25 % is sufficient to represent the total population.

According to Haque (2010), this sampling technique minimizes the sampling error and enables the inclusion of all characteristics of the population.

Table 1: sampling scheme and sample size

Name of newspaper	Population	% Proportion of each stratum in the population calculated	% Proportion multiplied by sample decided	sample size taken	Number of stories
Addis Admass	16 issues	9.52%	$9.52*42=3.99$	4	15
Addis Zemen	120 issues	71.43%	$71.43*42=30.00$	30	83
The Reporter	32 issues	19.05%	$19.05*42=8.00$	8	24
Total	168	100		42	122

3.4.1.3. Stratified Random Sampling. After the size of samples using proportionate sampling for each stratum was decided, a stratified random sampling technique was employed to select the issues of newspapers to be included under study. Accordingly, the newspaper issues were selected by date of publications randomly to give each issue an equal chance of being selected. However, Since *Addis Zemen* is daily and it is published 7 days a week and 30 days a month the issue of dates was randomly selected, while *Addis Admass* and

the reporter are weekly and bi-weekly respectively, only the days of publications (i.e., Saturdays for *Addis admass*, and Sundays and Wednesdays for *The Reporter*) were included in the random selection process as shown in the table below

Table 2: Newspaper issues selection by date of publication

Name of Newspapers	Newspaper issues sampled by date and Months of publications				Total
	<i>Tahisas</i>	<i>Tir</i>	<i>Yekatit</i>	<i>Megabit</i>	
<i>Addis Zemen</i>	1,6,9,18,19,21,26, &29	4,10,14,16,18,19,24	6,8,12,13,16,21,27, &30	1,7,10,15,20,22, &24	30 issues
<i>Addis Admass</i>	3	22	6	25	4 issues
<i>The Reporter</i>	7&,11	5&26	7, &10	29, &26	8 issues
					<u>42 issues</u>

3.5. Data Collection Methods

3.5.1 Quantitative Content Analysis (*QuanCA*)

Content analysis is a research technique for making replicable and valid inferences from texts (or other meaningful matter) to the contexts of their use (Krippendorff, 2004). Different scholars argue over the categorization of the content analysis as quantitative and qualitative. For instance, Krippendorff, (2004), argues that content analysis is a quantitative method even when it results in statistical conclusions as long as reading a text/a content is a qualitative process. He further contends that other authors' definition of content analysis is being quantified, and argues the effect of the statistical characteristics of mass-produced content on the audience which neither the audience nor the mass-producers are aware of. He objects to Berelson's idea of content being contained in messages waiting to be *separated*, instead, he states that content is subjected to multiple interpretations.

Other authors such as Hsieh & Shannon(2005), also define content analysis as a widely used qualitative research and of course three applications of it. The first approach is called conventional the second is called the direct and the third is summative. In the first case, ‘The major differences among the approaches lies in coding schemes, origins of codes, and threats to trustworthiness’. Accordingly, in the first case, coding categories are derived directly from the text data; in the second, the analysis starts with a theory or relevant research findings as guidance for initial codes; while the third approach involves counting and comparisons, usually of keywords or content, followed by the interpretation of the underlying context.

Neuendorf,(2017), in her part, defines content analysis as the systematic, objective, quantitative analysis of message characteristics.

Coe & Scacco(2017), also indicated that the data that emerge from the quantitative content analysis can be varied, however, regardless of its variety, the characters are described numerically. In this sense, quantitative content analysis can be understood as a method of describing the data in terms of numbers.

Other authors like White & Marsh, (2006) see content analysis as a flexible method that can be used as either qualitative or quantitative or ‘mixed’ method depending on the goals/objectives of the research.

Although there are debates over the categorization of qualitative-quantitative-dichotomy on content analysis, it is still one of the widely used research methods. Some of the scholars that contributed to the development of quantitative analyses as mentioned in Neuendorf (2004, p.39), are (Berelson,1952; Carney 1977; Weber 1990; Berger 1998; Smith 2000; Krippendorff, 2013; Riffe, Lacy, & Fico,2014; Babbie 2013). Neuendorf chooses to use content analysis as a quantitative approach and thereby stated the basis of qualitative and quantitative analyses. Quantitative analyses mainly rely on ‘the soundness of a priori

measurement instruments' while qualitative analyses usually depend on the knowledge of the investigator

To this end, the current researcher chose to use Krippendorff's definition of Content analysis as a research technique for making replicable and valid inferences from a text with all the procedures were attempted to employ to produce valid and replicable results. Besides, the current researcher used Neuendorf's definition of QuanCA as being a systematic, objective, quantitative analysis of texts.

3.5.1.1. Unit of Analysis. The unit of analysis, according to Wimmer & Dominick (2014), in the written content analysis might be a single word or symbol, a theme (a single assertion about one subject), or an entire article or story. Weber, (1990) also states that one of the important decisions any researcher must make is to define the coding unit.

For instance, Tankard(2001, p.100), established 11 means of identifying and measuring news frames. These are headlines, leads, subheads, photographs, photo captions, source selection, quotes, statistics, and charts, concluding statements, quote selection, pull quotes, and logos. The story is also used as a unit by this author and by many other content analysts.

Accordingly, the unit of analysis for this study were all available stories placed on the front page of the sample newspapers. The coding procedure was: read thoroughly into the stories until the theme of the story is identified. Thus except for some stories in which the themes were easily identified by simply reading the headlines, for the rest, it was important to read through the stories on the page where they were jumped to until the themes were clear.

3.5.1.2. Developing coding categories. According to Zhang & Wildermuth, (2009), the coding categories and schemes can emerge from three sources: these are the data, previous related studies, and theories. On the other hand, Wimmer & Dominick, (2011), indicated two ways of developing coding categories. These are emergent coding where the coding categories are established after a preliminary examination of the data; and prior

coding, where the categories are established based on the existing theoretical frameworks before the data analysis. Which are considerably similar to that of Zhang & Wildermuth, (2009) except for Wimmer & Dominick, (2011), who do not consider the previous and related studies as a source of developing categories.

Different scholars suggest different strategies of establishing categories, however, they all agree on categories being exclusive to one another. In the case of the current study, concerning types of the issue covered on the front-page, (eight (8) categories are adapted from (Biruk & Walia, 2019); one was taken from (Mulatu, 2017) with some revision and the rest of the categories are developed by the researcher. The categories were mainly pre-developed based on the objectives of the study intended to achieve.

In addition to the adapted categories, there are subcategories that the researcher added which are emerged from three major things that the newspapers were expected to cover in priority. These are social, economic, and political. Other categories, such as peace and security, issues are developed considering the country's recent conditions and the issues the researcher learned during the interview with the chief editors of the newspapers before the development of some categories.

Concerning, newsmakers/ sources, six categories were developed these are experts and professionals, celebrities, and public figures, politicians and government officials, Civil society organizations, ordinary citizens, and others, these are also the Newsmakers/actors who are most commonly appear in different studies.

3.5.1.2.1. Coders and the Coder Training. Two coders coded the content independently using the same coding manual (see appendix, A). Coder one was the principal researcher, and the second coder was a Journalism and Communication Lecturer At Dilla University, who was an MA in Journalism and Communication candidate at AAU during the

coding. Before any coding began, the researcher trained the co-coder well, until the coder was familiar with the instructions and categories.

3.5.1.2.2. Pilot study /reliability. The pilot reliability assessment is conducted after initial coder training and before the study begins. It should be done on a sample that is either a subsample of the full sample message pool or a separate sample from the population under investigation (Neuendorf, 2017, p. 242).

In the case of this study, 10 percent subsample from the full sample was done, during the pilot study, there was over $R = .80$ agreement on the subsamples the pilot conducted on, however, there were some, disagreements over, some categories. Accordingly, the categories were redefined; for instance, from the newsmakers/actor's category the category politicians were under the category celebrity and public figures category, later it was merged with government officials, and the civil society organizations category was added, so the categories were revised for the second intercoder reliability check. Measurements instruments

Stevens (1951) cited by Neuendorf, (2017) defined measurement as the assignment of numerals to objects or events according to rules. Neuendorf, (2017), used three concepts to measurement instruments. These are validity, reliability, accuracy, and precision.

Validity

Validity is the extent to which a measuring procedure represents the intended and only the intended concept. "In thinking about validity, we ask the question, are we measuring what we want to measure?" (Neuendorf, 2017, p. 172). In this regard, the categories were employed were validated in terms of both face and content appropriateness. Categories employed were reviewed by the advisors. Besides, the categories were adapted from previous studies and were readjusted based on the objectives the study intended to achieve.

Reliability

Reliability is the extent to which a measuring procedure yields the same results on repeated trials. This includes several types, including the notions of internal consistency of multiple indicators (as in a scale or index) and several types of coder reliability (p.173).

Intercoder reliability

To calculate the inter-coder reliability, the researcher employed Holst's most common formula for determining the reliability of nominal data in terms of percentage agreement cited in Wimmer & Dominick, (2014, p.175).

The formula is:

$$\text{Reliability} = \frac{2M}{N_1 + N_2}$$

Where M is the number of coding decisions on which two coders agree and N_1 and N_2 are the total numbers of coding decisions by the coders.

Accordingly, the following inter-coder reliability was reported in the final reliability in major four categories by independent coders as shown below the table.

Table 3: Inter Coder Reliability

Category I	Total decisions made		No.	Category II: News values	Total decisions made	
	A	B			Coder A	Coder B
			1	Timelines	41	41
	A	B	2	Conflict	4	15
Themes	8	8	3	Impact	2	15
Business, Economic, and finance issues	5	5	4	Prominence	3	3
			5	Relevance	4	3
			6	Proximity	2	2
Government administration /politics	29	29	7	Unseal/oddity	0	0
			8	Newspaper agenda	0	0
Social and legal issues	16	16	9	Good news	2	2
Entertainment and media	4	4		Bad news	2	2
International issues	2	1	R =.80			

Science and technology	1	1	
Environment Climate change	1	1	
Others	1	1	
R=.87			

Table 3.1: inter-coder reliability check

CategoryIII: Actors/newsmakers	Experts and Professionals	Politicians and Government officials	Civil society organization	Celebrity and public figures	Ordinary people	Others
Total decisions made						
Coder A	10	41	2	2	2	1
Coder B	14	41	2	2	4	1
Reliability	R=0.83					

When using Holst's formula 90% and the above-reported reliability are acceptable, while in other formulas such as pi or kappa= .81 to 1.00 indicating "almost perfect" agreement, Coefficients of .90 or greater are nearly always acceptable, .80 or greater is acceptable in most situations, and .70 may be appropriate in some exploratory studies for some indices (Wimmer & Dominick, (2014, p.180).

3.5.2 Interview

Interviews are one of the most commonly used and most basic research techniques. This research employed an in-depth interview, as it is a crucial research method for uncovering individual's attitudes and values towards the issue. As Wimmer & Dominick, (2011), also stated qualitative research involves several methods of data collection, such as focus groups, field observation, where the in-depth interview is one of them. This study gathered qualitative data using an in-depth interview with the chief editors of the study newspapers. The chief editors of the newspapers were selected using purposive sampling. The researcher believes and as it is demonstrated in the literature, selecting a certain issue or, certain newsmakers over the others, placing pictures, placing a certain story somewhere on

the top of the page or down, etc., is highly the role of the editors. Therefore, to uncover how and why the editors prioritize certain things at the expense of others, the researcher selected the editor in chiefs of the sample newspapers.

3.6. Methods and Procedures of Data Analysis

3.6.1. Quantitative Data Analysis

After reading thoroughly into the articles that appeared on the front pages of the sample issues, the data were coded into categories using the code sheet (see, Appendix A, and B). Then, the final inter-coder reliability was checked. Next, the data were prepared for analysis using the data entry sheet. After the data was clean and ready, they were fed into the SPSS tool and the data were analyzed using descriptive statics/frequencies. Then, the frequencies/percent output of SPSS were demonstrated in means of tables. Finally, the interpretation and conclusions were made based on those outputs.

3.6.2. Qualitative Data Analysis

Apart from the quantitative content analysis, the interviews were conducted with key informants two chief editors and one senior reporter. The interview was guided by a list of semi-structured questions (see Appendix C). The interviews were conducted in Amharic, which was recorded during the interviews for it was convenient to use it during the analysis. After listening to recorded data, were transcribed into text, the transcribed data were prepared for analysis (i.e., it was translated into English), then it was compared and triangulated with the finding of quantitative data.

3.7. Ethical Issues

Before collecting data from the media houses, the researcher approached the management of the selected newspapers and stated the intended purpose of the interview, as the permission was granted after the permission was granted and the researcher set an appointment to interview at the office of the media houses.

In doing, so the researcher managed to interview the two, newspapers' Chief Editors (*Addis Zemen*, and *The Reporter*). However, the attempt to interview the Chief Editor or deputy Chief Editor of *Addis Admass* newspaper was not successful despite the uninterrupted efforts made. The researcher went to the mentioned media house office (*Admass advertising, PLC*, located at *Kaznchis, Addis Ababa*), for about two weeks. Finally, the researcher decided to interview the senior Reporter, who worked for about 8 years. The absence of the editor-in-chief did not affect the analysis, since the senior reporter responded well to the questions since the researcher managed to interview the Chief Editors of *Addis Zemen* and *The Reporter* newspapers.

Chapter Four

Data presentation, Analysis and Interpretation

Introduction

This chapter presents the data collected through both the quantitative content analysis and an in-depth interview with the editors. As the focus of the study was to assess the type of issues featured; the type of actors appearing; and, news values employed on the front pages of the sampled newspapers between the period *Tahisas 1- megabit 30, 2013 E.C* (10 December 2020 to March 8, 2021).

The data analyzed via SPSS was presented in means of tables in terms of the frequencies and percentages, and then it was analyzed and interpreted sensibly. Then the findings of the content analysis were compared with the findings of the interview.

4.1 Quantitative data analysis

4.1.1. The Content Analysis

4.1.1.1. *Types of issues Covered on the Frontpage of the Newspapers*

To identify which issues were covered on the front page the researcher used eight pre-developed categories (i.e., business, economic, and finance; government, administration, and politics; social and legal; entertainment and media; international issues; science and technology; environment and climate change issues; the last category was other. Out of which the government, administration and politics, and social and legal issues were further categorized into 5 and 8 subcategories respectively. These subcategories are mutually exclusive and it was for clarity.

The subcategories of government, administration, and politics was further categorized into subcategories: politics, maladministration and corruption, development, peace and security, and conflict issues.

The social and legal issues category was further categorized into subcategories. These were: youth, women and children, people with disabilities, health issues, education, humanitarian and volunteering issues, culture. Heritage and history, religious issues, and crime, violence, and court issues.

Table 4 The extent of issues covered on the front pages the three of newspapers

Code assigned	Newspapers' Name						
	Categories	<i>Addis Zemen</i> N=83		<i>The Reporter</i> N=24		<i>Addis Admass</i> N=15	
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
1	Business economic/finance issues	5	6.0	5	20.8	2	13.3
2	Government/administration/politics	43	51.8	7	29.2	9	60.0
3	Social and legal issues	28	33.7	8	33.3	1	6.7
4	Entertainment and media	3	3.7	2	8.3	0	0
5	International issues	3	3.7	2	8.3	1	6.7
6	Science & technology	1	1.2	0	0	1	6.7
7	Environment & Climate change	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	Others	0	0	0		1	6.7
Total		83	100	24	100	15	100

Table 4.1: Issue Distribution across the Subcategories

Name of newspaper							
Categories	Subcategories	Addis Zemen		The reporter		Addis Admass	
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Government, administration, and politics	Politics	14	32.6	2	28.57	5	55.55
	Maladministration/corruption	1	2.3	1	14.28	0	0
	Development issues	8	18.6	0	0	0	0
	Conflict issues	9	20.9	3	42.85	4	44.44
	Peace and Security	11	25.6	1	14.28	0	0
Total		43	100	7	100	9	100
Social and legal issues	Youth, women, and children	2	7.1	0	0	0	0
	People with disabilities	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Health issues	5	17.85	1	12.5	0	0
	Education issues	3	10.71	2	25	0	0
	Humanitarian and volunteering issues	3	10.71	3	37.5	0	0
	Culture, heritage and history	6	21.42	0	0	0	0
	Religion and festivity issues	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Crime, violence, and court issues	9	32.14	2	25	1	100
Total		28	100	8	100	1	100

As shown in the above tables 4 and 4.1 the analysis was done on 122 stories that appeared on the front pages of the three newspapers of four months study period.

The type of issues covered on prominence by all the three newspapers are the *government, administration and politics, social and legal issues, and business, economic, and finance issues* comparatively. However, individually, there is some variation.

In *Addis Zemen*, the *government, administration, and politics* took the lion-share 43(51.8%) out of which the *political issues* 14(32. %), the highest coverage of the whole sub-themes/subcategories, and followed by *peace and security* 11(25.6%), *conflict* 9(20.9%), *development issues* 8(18.6%), and only 1 story (2.3%) was about

maladministration/corruption. The *social legal and legal issues* 28(33.3), took the next place with special emphasis on *Crime, violence, and court issues* 9(32.14%) and then followed, the *Culture, heritage, and history* 6(21.42) the *health issues* 5(18.75); the Education, and the humanitarian and volunteering issues 3(10.71%); the Youth, Women, and Children 2(7.1). The *business, economic, and finance issues* 5(6.0%) to the third place and 3 stories (3.7%) were about entertainment and media, and international issues, and 1 story (1.2%) about science and technology.

Addis admass gave prominence 9(60%) for the *government, administration with* special emphasis on *Political issues* 5(55.5) the *Conflict issues followed with* 3(44.4%). Next, the Government administration and politics came the business, economic, and finance issues 2(13.3%) and followed by the *social and legal issues/crime violence and court* 1(6.7%); *international issues* 1(6.7%); *science and technology* 1(6.7%); and *others* (6.7%).

The Reporter, however, gave prominence for the *social and legal issues coverage* 8(33.3%) with special emphasis on *humanitarian and volunteering issues* 3(37.5) and followed by the *crime, violence, and Court issues*, and *Education issues* both subthemes got an equal coverage of 2 stories (25%), of the total coverage of the category, and 1 story (12.5%) of the total coverage is covered on the health issue. Next to the *social and legal issues* came the *Government, administration, and Politics* 7(29.2), out of which 3 stories (42.8%) covered *conflict issues*; 2 stories (28.5%) *political issues*, and 2 stories (14.2%) each of which covered on *maladministration/corruption, and peace and security*. The *business economic and finance issues* took third place with 5 stories (20.8 %) covered, and 3 stories (8.3%) each of which covered the *entertainment and media and international issues*.

Analysis of the front page story pictures

Table 5: Use of pictures by newspapers

Items	<i>Addis Zemen</i>		<i>The Reporter</i>		<i>Addis Admass</i>	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Spot News	17	22.72%	3	11.53%	0	0
General News	51	68.92%	13	50%	3	42.85%
Feature Photographs	2	2.70%	7	26.92%	1	14.28%
Portraits/Personality Photo	1	1.35%	3	11.53%	1	14.28%
Sports Photograph	1	1.35%	0	0	0	0
Photo Story	0	0	0	0	0	0
Illustration	1	1.35%	0	0	2	28.57%
Total	74	100	26	100	7	100

As shown in table 5, as the frequency of publication of the newspapers varies there was also variation in using the pictures in the front-page stories. For instance, *Addis Zemen*(daily), used the highest number of pictures and also used a considerable number of Spot news pictures compared to the two newspapers. In *Addis Zemen*, 74 stories out of the 83 stories were presented with pictures. *The Reporter* also used 26 pictures where in some of the stories *The Reporter* (biweekly)used more than one picture for some stories. On the other hand, *Addis Admass* (weekly), used a small number of pictures, *Addis Admass* used the space to place more stories than pictures.

In terms of the types of pictures used by the newspapers, the general news photo was highly used. Comparatively, *Addis Zemen* came first scoring, 51(68.92), then followed *The Reporter* scoring 13(50%), and *Addis Admass* scoring, 3(42.85%).

Addis Zemen, 17(22.72%) and *The Reporter*, 3(11.53%). The other types of pictures used were: Feature photographs and portrait/personality types of pictures were used by all three newspapers. The portrait/personality type of photos were also identified in the three newspapers *The Reporter* was the first scoring 7(26.92%); *Addis Admass* came next scoring 1(14.28), and *Addis Zemen* came last scoring 2(2.07%). The portrait/personality photos were also used where *Addis Admass* took first place scoring 1(14.28%); next came *The Reporter* with 3(11.53); and lastly *Addis Zemen* scored 1(1.35%).

The illustration photos were identified in *Addis Admass*, 2(28.57%) and *Addis Zemen* 1(1.35%) while the sports photo was only identified in *Addis Zemen* once (1.35%).

In conclusion, *Addis Zemen* used the highest number of pictures in the front-page stories; followed by the reporter and Lastly *Addis Admass*. *Addis Zemen* used the highest number of pictures (3 pictures per page) and next came to the reporter (2 pictures per page). However, in the case of *Addis Admass*, there were not many pictures used. The fact that Editors of *Addis Zemen* placed more pictures than the two newspapers probably was that they have more spaces on the front page than *The Reporter* and *Addis Admass*. As matter of fact, *addis admass* used the space to place more stories on the front page.

Table 5.1: the Use of pictures on the front-page stories by types of issues

Types of Issues covered	the Use of pictures on the front-page stories by types of issues					
	<i>Addis Zemen</i>		<i>The Reporter</i>		<i>Addis Admass</i>	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Business economic/finance issues	6	8.1%	4	15.34%	1	14.28%
Government/administration/ Politics	42	56.75%	12	46.15%	4	57.14%
Social and legal issues	23	31%	7	26.92%	1	14.28%
Entertainment and media	1	1.35%	1	3.48%	0	0
International issues	2	2.07%	2	7.69%	0	0
Science & technology	0	0	0	0	1	14.28%
Environment & Climate change	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	74	100	26	100	7	100

As the finding indicates in table 5.1, the types of issues that were presented with pictures were the Government/administration/Politics Social and legal issues and Business economic/finance issues.

Addis Zemen used the highest number of pictures for the Government/administration/Politics issues accounts more than fifty percent of all the issues 42(56.75%) then followed the Social and legal issues with 23(31%) and Business economic/finance issues with (Business economic/finance issues 6(8.1%). 2 pictures (2.07%) and 1 picture (1.35%) were used for the international issues and the entertainment and media respectively.

The Reporter also used the largest number of pictures for Government/administration/Politics which accounts for 12(46.15%) the Social and Legal followed with 7(26.92%) and Business economic/finance issues came third with 4 (15.34%).

In terms of the types of issues present in pictures, there was no significant difference in *Addis Admass*. *Addis Admass* used 4 pictures (57.14%) for Government/administration/Politics; Next came the Social and social and legal issues, business Economic/finance issue, Science and technology issues at equal amount 1 picture (14.28%) each.

Table 5.2 The extent of newsmakers/Actors featured in the picture

Types of newsmakers/Actors	The extent of newsmakers/Actors featured in the pictures					
	<i>Addis Zemen</i>		<i>The Reporter</i>		<i>Addis Admass</i>	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Experts and professionals	4	5.4%	0	0	0	0
Politicians and Government officials	62	83.72%	23	88.45%	6	85.71%
Civil society organizations	0	0	0	0	0	0
Celebrity and public figures	3	4%	0	0	0	0
Ordinary people	3	4%	0	0	0	0
Others	2	2.7%	3	11.53%	1	14.28%
Total	74	100	26	100	7	100

As table 5.2, indicates, the newsmakers most frequently featured in the front pages pictured were Politicians and Government officials, experts and professionals, and others. Comparatively, *Addis Zemen* featured the highest number of Politicians and Government officials 62(83.72%), followed by Experts and professionals accounting 4(5.4%) and celebrity and public figures/Ordinary people at the same amount which accounts for 3(4%). As indicated in the table, there was no significant difference in using the newsmakers/actors among *Addis Zemen the Reporter*, and *Addis Admass*. The types of newsmakers appearing on

the front-page stories were the same. For instance, in *The Reporter* 23(85.45%) were Politicians and Government officials(11.53%) were others. In *Addis Admass*, the Government officials and Politicians account for 6(85.71%) and only one ordinary person's picture was featured.

Placement of stories on the front-page of newspapers

Table 6: story placement in Addis Zemen Newspaper

Types of issues	Story placement				Total
	Left top	Bottom left	Right top	Right bottom	
Business economic/finance issues	1	2	2	0	5
Government/administration/ Politics	17	9	7	10	43
Social and legal issues	10	5	3	10	28
Entertainment and media	2	1	0	0	3
International issues	1	2	0	0	3
Science & technology	1	0	0	0	1
Environment & Climate change	0	0	0	0	0
Other	0	0	0	0	0
Total					83

As indicated in Table 6 above, *Addis Zemen* placed most of the Government/administration/ Politics stories 17(39.53%), on the top left which is believed to be where the readers' eyes fixated at first; and in most cases where the main headline and the main picture of the edition is placed on. The stories that are placed on the bottom left (which is also the next important placement on the front page), were also Government/administration/ Politics stories which accounts for 9((20.93%). Next came the social and legal issues where 1 (35.7%) stories were placed on the left top and 5(17.85%) on the bottom left. Only 1(16%) Business economic/finance issues where the story was placed on the left top. Most of the Business economic/finance issues were placed on the bottom left and bottom right and 2(33.3%) stories on each. Therefore, the top priority stories of the *Addis*

Zemen were the Government/administration/ Politics stories followed by the social and legal issues.

Table 7: story placement in the Reporter Newspaper

Types of issues	Story placement				Total
	Left top	Bottom left	Right top	Right bottom	
Business economic/finance issues	2	2	0	1	5
Government/administration/ Politics	4	2	0	1	7
Social and legal issues	2	3	1	2	8
Entertainment and media	0	1	0	1	2
International issues	0	0	0	0	0
Science & technology		0	0	2	2
Environment & Climate change	0	0	0	0	0
Other	0	0	0	0	0
Total					24

As the finding indicated in the table above, *the Reporter*, placed most of the Government/administration/ Politics in Left top 4(57%) and bottom left (2 28.5%). Followed by Social and legal issues where 2(25%) on the left top and 3(37.5%); and Business economic/finance issues with 2(40%) stories were placed on both the left top and left bottom. The top priority stories in *The Reporter* were also Government/administration/ Politics followed by Social and legal issues and Business economic/finance issues.

Table 8: story placement in Addis Admass newspaper

Types of issues	Story placement				
	Left top	Bottom left	Right top	Right bottom	Total
Business economic/finance issues	1	1	0	0	2
Government/administration/ Politics	2	3	1	3	9
Social and legal issues	0	0	1	0	1
Entertainment and media	0	0	0	0	0
International issues	0	0	1	0	1
Science & technology	1	0	0	0	1
Environment & Climate change	0	0	0	0	0
Other	0	0	1	0	1
Total					15

As indicated in the table above, Addis Admass's issues preferences in terms of placement of stories on the front page, was the same as Addis Zemen and The Reporter with a slight difference. Accordingly, 2(22.2%) of Government/administration/ Politics issues were placed left top and 3(33.3%) were placed on the left bottom. Followed by Business economic/finance issues were 1(50%) both on the left top and left bottom. The social and legal issues were not as prioritized as in the other newspapers. The science and technology issue was placed on the left top; while the social and legal issue in Addis admass was placed on the right top page.

4.1.1.2. The Newsmaker/Actors in the Front-Page Stories

The researcher used 6 elaborated categories of newsmakers or actors which are more than just dichotomous categorizations of elite and non-elite, to identify who makes the front pages of the sampled newspapers. These are *experts and professionals; politicians and government officials, civil society organizations, celebrities, and public figures; ordinary people, and others*

Table 9: The Newsmakers/Actors in the Front-Page Stories

Newsmaker/actor Categories		Newspapers' Name					
		Addis Zemen N=83		The Reporter N=24		Addis Admass N=20	
No.		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
1	Experts and professionals	17	20.5	1	3.7	4	20.0
2	Politicians and Government officials	58	69.9	19	70.4	11	55.0
3	Civil society organizations	1	1.2	0	0	1	5.0
4	Celebrity and public figures	1	1.2	2	7.4	0	0
5	Ordinary people	6	7.2	1	3.7	3	15.0
6	Others	0	0	1	3.7	1	5.0
Total		83	100	24	100	20	100

As the above table shows, *the politicians and government officials actors* appeared most frequently on the front page of the newspapers. Comparatively, *the Reporter scored the highest percentage of politicians government officials-actors 19(70.4%), followed by Addis Zemen (69.9%), and Addis Admass 11(55%).*

The experts and professionals actors got the next prominence in *Addis Zemen* 17(20.5%), and *Addis Admass* 4(20%), while *The Reporter*, gave relatively small number 1(3.7%).

Addis Admass used the highest number of *ordinary people-actors* (15%), followed by *Addis Zemen*, while the *Reporter* relatively uses lower Ordinary people actors 2(7.4%).

The celebrity and public figures actors got a relatively good appearance in *The Reporter* 2(%), and appear once in *Addis Zemen* 1(1.2%).

Lastly, *the civil society organizations, actors* appear once (5%) in *Addis Admass* and *the Reporter* and (3.7), *Addis Zemen* (1.2%) while the other actors appear only in *Addis Admass* and *the reporter* once (5% and 3.7%) respectively.

4.1.1.3. The News Values Employed on the Front-Page Stories

Table 10: The extent of News Values Employed in front pages stories

News values		Newspapers' Name					
		Addis Zemen N=83		The Reporter N=27		Addis Admass N=27	
No.		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
1	Timeliness	60	72.3	15	55.6	7	25.9
2	Conflict	6	7.2	2	7.4	3	11.1
3	Impact	2	2.4	2	7.4	4	14.8
4	Prominence	2	2.4	2	7.4	4	14.8
5	Relevance	6	7.2	2	7.4	3	11.1
6	Proximity	0	0	2	7.4	2	7.4
7	Unusual/oddity	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	Newspaper agenda	4	4.8	0	0	0	0
9	Good news	2	2.4	0	0	0	0
10	Bad News	1	1.2	2	7.4	4	14.8
Total		83	100	27	100		100

As the above table shows, the newspapers employed timeliness dominantly, *Addis Zemen* being the first scoring 60(72.3%) followed by *The Reporter* scoring 15(55.6%), and *Addis Admass* scoring 7(25%).

Individually, in *Addis Zemen*, conflict, and relevance were the second frequently employed news values with 6 stories (7.2%) each followed by newspaper agenda 4(4.8%), impact, prominence, and good news 2(2.4%) each, and bad news 1(1.2%).

In *The Reporter*, next to the timelines, conflict, Impact, Relevance, proximity, and bad news were the second frequently employed, news values at evenly distributed frequency 2(7.4%).

In *Addis Admass*, bad news, impact, and prominence were offered the second prominence, 4(14.) each, followed by conflict, confused the larger number of conflict stories, scoring 3(11.1%), followed by conflict, and relevance 3(11.1%) each, and proximity 2(7.4%)

In conclusion, timeliness was predominantly employed by the three newspapers while conflict impact, and relevance, were employed at a second prominence. This implies that the editors select events as news for the front page. Even though during the interview, the informants mentioned the fact that covering the events such as meetings, conferences, press releases are not worth covering on the front page because they said that the newspapers cannot compete with social media which keeps breaking issues at any minute. However, practically, the timely issues or official disclosures in most cases on occasional issues or events were found to dominate the coverage. Next, the issues that involved conflict; topics that are considered to be relevant for the public; issues that are considered to impact the greater audience; and somehow, international issues that were reported with local context; and stories based on prominent personalities were given prominence. From Harcup & O'Neill (2017), news values that were included in the categories, the newspaper agenda, good news, and bad news were identified in the stories especially the bad news was given higher

prominence in Addis Admass. The Newspaper Agenda was given relatively good prominence by *Addis Zemen*. Common to all three newspapers, no story with odd/unusual occurrence was treated on the front page.

4.2. Analysis of The Qualitative Data

Regarding the type of issue and how the issues are selected; and the type of newsmakers/actors selected for the front page of the sampled newspapers, the researcher conducted a semi-structured in-depth interview with the chief editors. The following two questions guided the interview with the editors.

Q1: What makes front-page news for your publications? / What type of stories are usually preferred to be placed on the front? If any reason why?

Q2: Who makes the front-page news in your day's publication in terms of newsmakers? In connection are there any criteria for selecting a particular type of newsmaker?

4.2.1. Interview with the Chief Editor of Addis Zemen

First of all, *Addis Zemen* is a public newspaper, so we place news on the front page that has higher public interest and relevance, and readability to the public. On the other hand, we plan to make news based on occasional events. ...Especially since the last three years, the country is undergoing reform, so we also plan to write news on the reform, and reach the public (Anteneh H., Personal Interview, May 24, 2021).

When comparing the finding demonstrated in the content analysis, *Addis Zemen* prioritized the government, Administration, and political issues where out of 43 stories 14 are devoted to politics, and the social and the economic issues followed. The coverage is dominated by political content even the economic and the social issues covered have political themes. While as the interview, data shows that the editor of the newspaper claimed that *Addis Zemen* is a “public newspaper”, and prioritized public interest issues. Here, *Addis*

Zemen being the public newspaper seems a contradictory issue. As Skjerdal, (2012, p.96), indicated that it is problematic to apply the term ‘public media’ to the Ethiopian ‘state media’ because they do not fully fit into the Public Service Media’s tradition.

Another thing one can understand from the extract is, that the type of issues the newspaper considers important were of significant occasional events and issues related to the ‘reform’.

That shows the government agenda gets special emphasis.

Regarding the newsmakers/actors, the editors responded as follows:

Regarding the newsmakers; they may differ depending on the issue they are associated with; it might be the prime minister or any ordinary person with a topic of relevance. We do not choose newsmakers based on their political personality or popularity, what matters is the information they can tell. However, in most cases, politicians, policymakers, academics, in general people who have a certain official responsibility, or higher public curiosity are not only our regular customers but also are our news interpreters (Anteneh H., Personal Interview, May 24, 2021).

From the above extract of the interview, one can understand that there is a theory of choosing newsmakers/actors according to their relevance being reported to the issue.

However, practically, as the content analysis shows, the known actors are the most frequent sources. The unknowns appeared six times related to social and legal issues, education, peace, and security issues. This indicates that known actors (such as government officials) are highly preferred as a source over the unknowns (such as ordinary people), and the finding from the content analysis demonstrates that. For instance, politicians and government officials, and experts and professionals took over 90 percent of the share of the making the news. Therefore, it can be concluded that Addis Zemen, allows the known actors most frequently, to have a say over the unknowns. In fact, these actors are seen as not as a source also as news interpreters or shapers.

This implies two things, one, the editors prefer to feature known faces to the unknown ones. It is believed that the reader is curious about what knowns say. The second is that the phrase “our regular customer” may suggest that the knowns are contacted most frequently for

authoritative information. On the other hand, this is in some cases linked to Gans (2004), the notion about journalists and their sources ‘availability and suitability. Gans noted that the knowns or the powerful individuals could be easily accessed, by the journalists for information. Journalists make a judgment about the available information according to their time, space, and resource. However, it is unlikely for the unknowns to be recognized easily until they do something that results in a serious consequence in society.

4.2.2. Interview with the Chief Editor of the Reporter Newspaper

We select the crucial issues among major issues that happened in the week across the country regardless of the tone of the issues: be it bad or good. Concerning the type of issues, political issues are preferable. Obviously, there is nothing that politics does not touch upon. For example, when you talk about the economy, or the living cost, or inflation, you blame the government or the administration, so in this case, the economy is linked to policy and politics (Tamiru T., Personal Interview, May 24, 2021).

The above extract from the interview shows that the news that the editor places on the front page are crucial issues. The type of issue that the newspaper editor prefers are political issues, according to him, politics touches different issues. The latter claim seems not limited to the reporter, mixing other issues with politics, is evident chiefly in *Addis Zemen* and somehow in *Addis admass* too.

As a matter of fact, the reporter gave prominence to the *social and legal issues/humanitarian and volunteering issues*, and next comes to the *government, administration and politics/conflict issues* dominates, however common to all the three newspapers, politics is a preferred type of issue for the front page, over the other type of “crucial issues” that happen during a given publication week.

Concerning the newsmakers/actors of the FrontPage of the reporter newspapers the chief editor responded as follows.

Regarding newsmakers/actors, we choose in two ways. One is, that when we write news on the major issues that happen during the publication week, by talking to the concerned bodies, be it, government officials, or the owner of a private company, or any person associated with the issue. The second, one, is that we consider outsourcers, who tip off information, in that case, we keep their names anonymous (Tamiru T., Personal Interview, May 24, 2021).

The editor of the reporter responded in the same way that of Addis Zemen's Editor, both editors stated that actors are selected according to their association with the issue being reported. The difference was the fact that the Editor of *Addis Zemen* mentioned using unknown actors, or anonymous actors, which was not evident in the content analysis of this study period. Furthermore, the finding from the content analysis shows that the reporter used the highest number of known actors the politicians and government officials followed by the celebrity and public figures-actors. Indeed, the unknowns, appeared only once, related to the social and legal issue (illegal trade).

4.2..3. Interview with the senior Journalist of Addis Admass Newspaper

The stories that appear on our newspaper's front page are occasional and crucial issues regardless of the issue type. The issues may be health, political, social, or economic issues. As you can see, in our country, the political area is changing, so, political issues may dominate the front-page coverage (Nafkot Y., Personal Interview, June 1, 2021).

As one can understand from the above extract from the interview, the issues that make the front page of *Addis Admass* are significant issues that happen within the publication week. Even though covering the crucial occasional issues, politics may dominate the front-page coverage of the newspaper.

As also demonstrated in the content analysis, *Addis Admass* prioritized *the government, administration, and politics/ politics issues*.

Regarding the newsmakers, the senior reporter responded as follows:

[...] well, they may differ as the issue we cover differs. For instance, if the issue is politics, we talk to the government officials or the opposition political party leaders, or political scientists. If the issue is about the cost of living, we talk to the public, and people around the trade area. Or if it is a health issue, we talk to patients, and health professionals (Nafkot Y., Personal Interview, June 1, 2021).

Again, the data from the interview are the same as the finding from the content analysis. The finding shows *Addis Admass* newspaper used the highest number of known actors and involved a relatively fair number of ordinary people actors when it compared to the other two newspapers.

Even though the data from the interview shows that unknown actors can have a say on different issues, in practice, the content analysis, demonstrated that the known actors highly dominate the coverage. As stated in the interview, these ordinary people who appeared on the front page of *Addis Admass* were associated with the issues like, cost of living, and other issues (residents' complaints about environmental sound pollution).

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Chapter Five

Summaries, Conclusions and Recommendations

Introduction

In the previous chapter, the data gathered through both quantitative content analysis and the interview were presented, analyzed, and triangulated sensibly. This chapter, summarizes and concludes the major findings, and lastly forwards the recommendations, based on findings.

The purpose of this study was to assess the front-page issue coverage of three Ethiopian Amharic newspapers (*Addis Zemen*, Government-own daily, *The Reporter*, privately owned Biweekly, and *Addis Admass*, privately-owned weekly).

5.1. Summaries

Concerning, the issues the newspapers covered on the front page, the data revealed that the newspapers prioritized the major occasional issues coverage; of the occasional events that happen during the publication week editors prefer to cover the government and political issues, with a slight variation with the Reporter's coverage. *The Reporter* newspaper prioritized the social and legal issues with an emphasis on humanitarian/volunteering issues followed by the government/political issues.

In terms of newsmakers/actors the known actors (in this case, politicians and government officials plus experts and professionals and celebrity and public figures at some level), were most frequently appeared. Even though having diverse viewpoints in the news is a crucial issue in journalism, the newspapers rarely entertained a diversity of viewpoints. In comparison, *Addis Admass* offered prominence to the unknowns. The issues associated with unknown newsmakers/actors were the cost of living and, environmental issues, etc. In a general sense, for unknowns to be considered as newsmakers, either they must involve in serious chaos such as committing a serious crime, or a serious action happens to them such as

being displaced or victimized. While the known actors were allowed to have their say in any issue, in ways such as giving comments, opinions, giving official statements, etc.

In terms of news values employed, timeliness was the predominantly employed news value by the three newspapers. The timely issues, mostly official disclosures, were selected as news. Conflict, impact, relevance, and prominence were the secondly employed news values.

Concerning the use amount of the news pictures, as much as the frequency of the publication of the newspapers varies. *Addis Zemen* run 3 pictures; *the reporter* 2 pictures; *addis Admass* 1 picture per page respectively.

In *Addis Zemen* newspaper, the largest number of pictures were used, however, most of the pictures used were general news story pictures which were mainly associated with political events, Press Conference, occasional happenings, etc. even though the editors of *Addis Zemen* newspaper used many pictures, however, some of the pictures were compressed and were not aesthetically appealing. Furthermore, the newsmakers/actors frequently appearing on the front-page pictures were Government officials and politicians which made the page unappealing.

In terms of the types of pictures used; the types of issues associated; and the type of newsmakers/actors featured in the pictures, *The Reporter* and *Addis Admass* newspapers were not much different from *Addis Zemen* except for *Addis Admass* used a small number of pictures and placed bolder headlines in place of pictures.

Concerning the placement of stories on the front page, the placement of stories were identified into four placements the left-top (potentially the first area the reader sees) Bottom left; (the next destination for the readers' eyes), the third, and the fourth are the top right and the bottom right pages respectively. Accordingly, as the finding revealed most of the stories placed on the top left and bottom left were the government/administration/politics and followed by the social and legal issues; and business /economic/finance issues.

5.2. Conclusions

Based on the major findings the following conclusions were made:

Therefore, the researcher concluded the issues that were perceived important by the sample newspapers were the government, administration and politics; social and legal issues, and business, and finance issues comparatively. Furthermore, the newspapers attempted to emphasize the crucial occasional issues, such as peace and security, conflict, humanitarian issues.

Concerning the newsmakers/actors in the news, it is concluded that the sample newspapers failed to entertain a variety of voices. The most frequent newsmakers/actors featured in the front-page stories were known newsmakers/actors (the government officials and the experts and professionals). The unknown newsmakers/actors such as ordinary people barely appeared in the front-page stories. In comparison, *Addis admass* entertained a considerable number of unknown newsmakers/actors.

Regarding, the news values employed the news values researcher concluded that the Timeliness, conflict, and impact type of stories were dominant news values employed in the front-page stories of the sample newspapers. Timeliness type of stories dominated the coverage because the newspapers covered the occasional crucial issues; news releases, conferences, and speeches.

Therefore, the researcher understood from the findings, more or less all the three newspapers offered good coverage on different perceived crucial issues, regardless of their ownership (i.e., being government-owned, or privately-owned).

5.3. Recommendations

Based on the above conclusions the following recommendations are forwarded.

Recommendation for further studies on the same topic:

- Due to financial and time constraints, this study was conducted on small data, short study period, so, it is recommended for incoming researchers to do a study on larger data and longer period so that the result could be concluded to the larger population.
- This study was limited to studying only the media issue salience. The first-level agenda setting guided the study. For this study considered as complete agenda-setting study, it had to incorporate a readership survey or public opinion on the major issues that the media considered important. Therefore, for future researchers who are interested in the agenda-setting study, studying media issue salience and the public issue salience (media agenda and public agenda) is recommendable.
- For someone, who is interested in conducting a further study on the newspapers, the newspaper's front-page designs are also, relatively unexplored areas.
- There are, studies that compare the content prioritization of the print and the online editions of the newspapers conducted in other countries, it will be another area of study to conduct in the Ethiopian context.

Recommendations for the media:

- The newspapers cover, important occasional issues, or issues with, perceived national significance, however, they failed to have a variety of voices in the stories. Therefore, it is recommended to have multiple actors in the story as it provides the reader with a variety of perspectives and it is a quality of doing good journalism.

- The front page is the prime page. It is like what a prime time for TV news is, according to different literatures, and as the editors were aware of that which researcher learned during the interview. However, the front page of the sample newspapers were not as catchy as it was supposed to be.
- Therefore, the editors should avoid using unchancy long, and messy, headlines (which are primarily reflected in *Addis Zemen*, and somehow in *The Reporter* and *Addis Admass*). The editors instead are recommended to use short larger, catchy headlines, excellent photos, and diverse faces.
- Since pictures are an excellent way of depicting reality and attracting the readers; the editors should use a variety of excellent pictures that can attract the readers and convey the desired message.
- The pictures used on the front page frequently by the newspapers were of the same type of personalities (in most cases authorities), which this repetitive use of the same people made the page unattractive. Instead, including some creative pictures and featuring different faces and voices is recommended.

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Appendixes

Appendix A: Coding manual for content analysis

Name of Coder:

Write the initials of your name and surname if there is an initial overlap of initials among coders, use two initials for the first names.

Name of the newspaper

Addis Admass-AA-01

Addis Zemen- AZ-02

The Reporter- TR-03

Newspaper issue date -DD/MM/YY- (6 digits)

e.g., Tahisas 11, 2013= 11/04/13

Issue of date: use the date of publication

Year: 2013

Months:

Tahsas (December) - 04

Tir (January)_____05

Yekatit (February)-06

Megabit (March)-07

SN^o = Story Number: number the stories on each issue of the paper as appearing from left top margin to down and then right top margin to down. (Using ,01,02,03, 04, etc.,) The headline of the Story: write the headline of a given story on the issue.

Coding Categories and Scheme

Guidelines (the researcher consulted, Lynch & Peer, 2002), in developing instruction and categories

I. Themes

Instructions

While you are coding the theme of the stories, most stories may confuse you or involve more than one theme. So, consider the following points.

The questions to ask are:

- *What is this story really about?*
- *Which theme is prioritized, emphasized?*
- *What is the main point in the story?*
- *What is the central concept described in the story?*

To answer these questions, use the following guidelines:

Code any story that appears on the front page and directs you to somewhere inside the paper a story continues (e.g., if it says, *jump to page...*).

2. While you code a story, focus on why this story is in the paper at all – usually, something has to happen (a news peg) that can give you a clue on how to classify the story.
3. Use headlines or subheads or the people appearing on the photo as clues only: the theme of the story may not be identified by its headline, so read into it until the central theme is identified.
4. Do not code contents such as graphs, promos/teasers, ads, indexes, info graphs, etc,
5. Discuss the story with another coder if you're still uncertain.

Themes

1. Business/Economic/financial issues: this implies unemployment levels, job opportunities, the establishment of new industries, plantations, living costs, stock market, foreign investment, trade, economic declines/crisis, taxes, privatization, success, failure, Ethiopian business projects by Ethiopian businesspeople, any story of any economic or finance theme

Government /administration /Politics (select category)

201.Politics: The basic question here to ask is that, is the story all about political agenda in favor of the other issues? for example, the story may mention about economy or society but if the story devotes much attention to the political implication that probably has a political theme; or the story may be about one of the following or related issues

This may include the political decision makings, policy issues, etc., by the ruling party, the opposition party, political party- leaders, higher government officials; or other related issues

such as election, political demonstrations, party generated-events, political policy introductions, or implementation issues, appointments officials for office, political meetings, interviews with political personalities. etc,

202. Maladministration/corruption issues: stories about, lack of good governance, investigation of wrongdoing of the government officials, or companies, etc.,

203. Development issues: This refers to stories covered on development activities in a variety of sectors (i.e., agriculture, industry, services): e.g., construction of roads, hospitals, clean water accessories, building like condos, dams (more importantly the GERD), electricity, the progress in services. e.g., Hotels, etc, agricultural progresses e.g., crop production and other facilities and infrastructures.

204. Conflict issues: This may include conflicts between two groups, or among groups, communities, protests against the government and opposition forces; conflict between the government and regional or part of the regional administrations, etc... as a result of conflicting interests, (i.e., fights over power dominance, land, and natural resources), etc, that leads to different forms and levels of chaos: loss of citizens lives; damage of property; displacement of citizens; peace and security threats, famine cut of social services, such as health, water, electricity.

205. Peace and security: These may include stories about the relations between regional states and their people, meetings on peace and security; visits paid by the community to another community; resolving conflicts of a different type, i.e., ethnic, religious, or different interest groups and other issues concerning national peace and stability, in a general sense, actions taken by the government or others to ensure the wellbeing of citizens.

3. Social and legal issues (select category): stories about the society, one of the following mentioned issues

301 Youth, Women and Children: any stories about women's participation, youths, and children in focus

302. people with Disabilities: any story that is all about disabled groups in focus

303. Health issues: this may refer to health problems (including health advice to alleviate health problems/conditions), quality of hospitals and clinics, cost of health care, natural disaster, child malnutrition, pollution, health insurance, women and health, medicine-science development.

304. Education: This may include issues about education, schools, universities, colleges, researches findings, students, academic seminars, graduations, academic promotions, interviews with, presidents, instructors, or students or other employees of the institutions or about any of educational institutions such as MoSHE.

305. Humanitarian/ human right/volunteering issues: stories about NGOs engagement in humanitarian aid, Voluntary people, and deeds, human right violations; human right concerns and dialogues, protection activities by local and international concerned organizations, aids, supports provided to the needy, calls for supports, fundraising events, meetings. Etc

306 Culture/heritage/and history: this implies globalization or westernization, honoring persons, food, clothing, nations and nationalities, historical sites, family life.

307. Religious/festivity issues: stories covered on religious matters, festivals, rituals related to major religions, or other celebrations of a non-religious kind

308 Crime, Violence, and Court issues: Stories covered on crime and justice-related issues: such as detainees, crime victims, court cases, the arrest of suspects, crime investigation, court trials, robbery, human and democratic rights violations, illegal trade activities, atrocities and perpetrators, and other issues that found to be against the law.

4. Entertainment and media: This includes, movie critics, review, movie release news, etc, Television shows, media, or personality news, talk; Music album release, concert; Fashion show and personalities; Book launch, review, etc; Celebrity News, etc. or sports, or any sort of entertainment elements.

5. International affairs: All issues that have international settings (at least if the story involves more than one sovereign nation regardless of issue types, i.e., political economy, society, environment), or other issues about, international relations, peace talks, peace deal, protests/ demonstrations, sanctions, antagonism between nations, international law, terrorism, illegal weaponry, etc.

Science and technology: it implies the creation of new technology in the country, introduction or the significance of adopting of new technology in various sectors, etc.

7. Environmental /climate change: this may refer to climate change influences on the environment, agriculture, forestation, geography, desertification, drought, the amount of rain, etc., in the country, or the world, and what is being done to cope with it other related issues.

8. Others: Use this category as the last resort and justify, how the items do not fit into the rest of the above categories

II. Actors/News-makers

Experts and professionals: Experts in a certain field of study, such as Academics, health professionals media professionals, or journalists, business or economics professionals, etc..., people with expertise and experience in a certain area.

2. Government officials and Politicians: this includes opposition party leaders or ruling party leaders speak on behalf of their political party, political programs/policies; political activists, or other political personalities who are allowed to speak their political ideology, program, or comment on political issues or may include authorities who are in Charge of Government institutions, government officials, law enforcement officers, who appear in the story as official sources.

3. Celebrity and public figures/: this may include well-known people: artists, musicians, actors, authors, social media personality, or business leaders, religious leaders, elderly people, sportspersons, human right activists, etc, who has a social position, and acceptance in the public.

4. Civil Society Organizations: includes unions, associations outside of political parties and government institutions e.g., such as trade unions, social movements, NGOs, or other interest groups

5. Ordinary people: this category one of the following includes, or more

- Residents/ residents of a certain area, who appear in the news
- Employees: Employees of a certain company, institution, etc.
- Victims: eyewitnesses of e certain crime, violence, disaster, etc.,
- Farmers/: farmers speaking of their farm, crop or crop production, or life in the countryside
- traders/vendors Any common People, who participates in any trading activities

6. Others: Use this category as the last resort and justify (you can use the “comment” section in the code sheet), how the items do not fit into the rest of the categories

III. News Values

1. Timelines: stories that are written of recently, happen, or happen shortly.

2. Conflict: stories about Strife, antagonism, and warfare, ethnic clashes, conflict of interests among individuals or groups, controversies, arguments, and fights.

3. Impact: Events that are likely to affect many people; Stories that are perceived as sufficiently significant that include greater numbers of people involved and impact the greater number of people.

4. Prominence: stories written of public figures, well-known people, celebrities, etc...

5. Relevance: Stories about issues, groups, and nations perceived to be relevant to the audience

6. Proximity: Events that are geographically or emotionally close to people

7. Unusual/oddity: Events that deviate sharply from the expected, that departs considerably from the experiences of everyday life make news

8. Newspaper agenda: Stories that set or fit the news organization's agenda, Whether ideological, commercial or as part of a specific campaign.

9. Good news: Stories with particularly positive overtones such as recoveries, breakthroughs, cures, wins, and celebrations.

10. Bad News: Stories with particularly negative overtones such as death, injury, defeat, and loss (of a job, for example)

The front-pages of the selected Ethiopian Newspapers: a critical analysis of Addis

Zemen, the reporter Amharic, and Addis Admass

Appendix B: Coding sheet for collecting data from newspapers

Story Analysis Form

Fill out the form per issue as per the definition and instructions assigned for each variable on the coding manual

Coder _____

Name of newspaper (use code) _____

Issue date: _____

SN° _____

Headline _____

Theme use code _____

Subcategory (if any) use code _____

Comment _____

News values: you can identify more than one,

Write the codes on the space below as many as identified in the story _____

Actors/newsmakers: you can identify more than one writes the codes on the space below as many as identified in the story _____

**Appendix C: Guide Questions for in Depth Interview with the Editors of the
sample newspapers**

1. What makes front-page news for your publications? / What type of stories are usually preferred to be placed on the front? If any reason why
2. Who makes the front-page news in your day's publication in terms of newsmakers?
3. What are the news values and criteria for selecting such stories? /Are there any news values unique to your newspaper to decide what news is?
4. What role does the editor play in terms of what goes on the front page?
5. How do you choose the newsmakers? In connection are there any criteria for selecting a particular type of newsmaker?
6. Which type of news values do you employ to select the newsworthiness of the stories?
Why?
7. Does the newspaper have a policy of ensuring representativeness in terms of what?

Gets published

AppendixD: the Amharic version interview guide questions

1. በየ እትሞችሁ ለጋዜጣችሁ (frontpage) የፊት ገጽ ዜናነት የሚሟሟ ጠቅላይ ምን አይነት ርዕስ ጉዳዮች ናቸው?
2. ዜናዎችን ስለ የምትመርጡ ጠቋችሁ በምን መሰረት የዜና/አላባወጃን (nvs) ነው? /ለናንተ ጋዜጣ ብቻ ልዩ የሆኑ የዜና እሴቶች ይኖሩ ይሆን? ካሉስ ምን ምን ናቸው?
3. አብዛኛውን ጊዜ ምን አይነት ዜናዎች ናቸው ለፊት ገጽ ዜናነት የሚሟሟ ጠቅላይ? ምክንያቱስ ምን ድን ነው?
4. የፊት ገጽ በማወጣት ሂደት ወስጥ የአርታኢዎች ማገዝ ምን ድን ው?
5. የዜናዎቻችሁ ምን ጭቆና ወይም ዜና ማሰራጨት አይደለም ማን ናቸው ዜናዎችን?
6. አንድን ዜና አንድነት ነው የምትመርጡ ጠቅላይ: የትንኛዎቹን የዜና መግረጫ መሰረት ትጠቀማላችሁ?
7. ጋዜጣችሁ ብዙ ደምጻችን ከሚሰጡት ገደብ አንጻር ፖሊሲዎንም መመሪያ አላችሁ?

Appendix E: Coding Guide for Analyzing Pictures on the Front Page of the Newspapers

Instructions

Code all the news pictures that are accompanied by the headline; do not code the picture of ads or any picture element that are not part of the stories on the front page.

Identify the type of pictures as one of the following

01=Spot News: These are pictures that carry urgent, unplanned and often unpleasant or undesirable occurrences. Spot news pictures include car accidents, plane crashes, fires, murders, bank robberies, etc.

02=General News photojournalism: Unlike spot news, general news pictures are recorded events or planned events pictures and they are less time-sensitive they can be delayed and yet not go stale. Photographs on general news include politics, press, or social events, must portray something new or exhibit other news value such as prominence, magnitude, oddity, etc.

03=Features Photograph: Features provide a visual break from routine news pictures. They tell an old story in a new way or from a new point of view. Editors tend to use features when space is available and they have no images of a more severe and essential nature.

04=Portraits/personality photos: They are used to tell a person's story. Photojournalists shoot both posed and candid portraits to achieve this. Even when they are arranged elements for portraits, photojournalists look for honest, candid moments. Portraits reveal something about a person's personality thus photojournalists strive to project this in their portrait pictures.

5=Sports Photograph: Sports photographers are like athletes, they uniquely strive to capture the fast-paced action and drama of competition. A sports picture summarizes the game in one photograph on time. The sports photographer captures interesting, unusual, emotional, and unexpected actions on and of the sports field.

06=Photo Story/pictorial journalism: This refers to editorial photographs that tell narrative stories. The story must be planned and well organized to present a complete detailed account of an interesting and significant subject, event, and personality aspect of contemporary life in a narrative form.

07=Illustration photo Journalism: this type of photo refers to combined or manipulated images that create a 'new' image. advertising photographers to illustrate stories based on issues and abstract ideas. Such as economics, science, etc. Photo illustrations communicate concepts a literal picture is not always able to.

Appendix F: Front Page Pictures of Newspapers

Front Page Pictures of *Addis Zemen* Newspaper

	Date of issues E.C	Types of pictures							Total
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
1	1/04/13	1	2	-	-	-	-	-	3
2	6/04/13	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	3
3	9/04/13	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	2
4	18/04/13	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	2
5	19/04/13	-	2	1	-	-	-	-	3
6	21/04/13	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	2
7	26/04/13	2	1	-	-	-	-	-	3
8	04/05/13	1	2	-	-	-	-	-	3
9	10/05/13	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
10	14/05/13	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	3
11	16/05/13	1	2	-	-	-	-	-	3
12	18/05/13	1	2	-	-	-	-	-	3
13	19/05/13	-	3	1	-	-	-	-	4
14	24/05/13	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	2
15	06/06/13	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1
16	8/06/13	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	2
17	12/06/13	-	4	-	-	-	-	-	4
18	13/0/613	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	2
19	16/06/13	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	2
20	21/06/13	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	4
21	27/06/13	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	2
22	30/0613	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	3
23	01/07/13	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	3
24	7/07/13	1	2	-	-	-	-	-	3
25	10/07/13	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	2
26	15/07/13	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
27	20/07/13	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	2
28	22/07/13	-	2	-	-	1	-	-	2
29	24/07/13	-	2	-	1	-	-	-	3
30	29/07/13	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	2
Total		17	51	2	1	1	0	3	74

Front Page Pictures of The *Reporter* Newspaper

	Date of issues E.C	Types of pictures							Total
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
1	7/04/13	-	2	-	1	-	-	-	3
2	11/04/13	-	2	-	2-	-	-	-	4
3	5/05/13	-	2	1	-	-	-	-	3
4	26/05/13	1	2	-	-	-	-	-	3
5	7/06/13	-	1	4	-	-	-	-	5
6	10/06/13	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	2
7	26/07/13	-	2	2	-	-	-	-	4
8	29/07/13	2	2	-	-	-	-	-	3
Total		3	13	7	3	0	0	0	26

Front Page Pictures of Addis Admass Newspaper

	Date of issues E.C	Types of pictures							Total
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
1	3/04/13	-	2	-	1	-	-	-	3
2	22/05/13	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1
3	6/06/13	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1
4	25/07/13	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	2
Total		-	4	1		1		1	7